

FEAST

Dissemination Exploitation & Communication

Update
02

DEC

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Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

Table 1 Document history of changes

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication Date	Changes
1.0	30.06.2025	

Key Facts

Action Number: 101060536

Action Acronym: FEAST

Action title: Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs

Date: 30.06.2025

DEC version: 3.0

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Table 2 *List of acronyms and abbreviations*

CoP	Community of Practice
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GDP	Gross domestic product
GHG	Greenhouse gas
LL	Living Lab
MAA	Multi Actor Approach
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OS	Open Science
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
USP	Unique Selling Point
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document provides an update to FEAST's DEC plan based on progress from M18-M35 of the project (the first version of FEAST's DEC plan is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11370487>)). The first updated DEC plan followed the same structure as the initial document (available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11370487>).

In this second DEC update, we have included a new chapter of best practices in the DEC activities designed and undertaken in FEAST.

Some key highlights since the last DEC update include:

- 19,382 visits, 45,382 pageviews and 1,257 downloads, 1,149 unique downloads of content on FEAST's website
- 1047 users (09.06.2025) following FEAST's activities and posts on LinkedIn (at least one post/week)
- 57 videos produced and published on FEAST's YouTube channel, which garnered 5,023 views and 27.7 K impressions, of which 87.7% of the views were from visitors who were not subscribers to FEAST's YouTube channel
- Five internal knowledge exchange webinars were held on a variety of policy and non-policy related topics
- FEAST partners have presented the project's outputs at 22 European events and meetings
- More than 50 registrations, representing 14 unique city regions, for FEAST's Community of Practice

	Activity	Objective of activity	State of implementation & current status
COMMUNICATION	Website	To give FEAST web visibility, provide further background information and updates on project progress.	Started in July 2022 – Ongoing: Main FEAST pages include 12 distinct pages, linking to 75 subpages.
	Internal newsletter	To inform FEAST partners about updates within the WPs as well as updates on important external news.	First release January 2023 – Ongoing: Every quarter, four times per year.
	External newsletter	To inform FEAST newsletter subscribers about updates from FEAST.	First release April 2023 – Ongoing: Every six months, twice per year. Overview of the past newsletter: Press Corner FEAST Three more external newsletters have been prepared and sent out in the last 12 months.
	Press releases	To update target audiences on FEAST outputs through journalists and mainstream media	First release August 2022 – Ongoing: At irregular intervals, but as soon as there is something to report to the press. Three press releases have been issued in the past 12 months.
	Brochures, booklets, flyer	To provide high-quality information about FEAST and its WPs through printed materials.	Started August 2022 – Ongoing: Frequency according to demand. The FEAST highlight brochure is a summary of project highlights, which is published once a year in October. The first edition was published in October 2023. <i>First Year Highlights, 2022/23</i> <i>Second Year Highlights, 2023/24</i> A FEAST flyer was created for conferences and dissemination events. It provides a brief overview of the project. Resources FEAST
	Meetings, webinars, dialogs	To inform and support FEAST	Started August 2022 – Ongoing: Frequency according to demand

<p>and workshops, podcasts</p>	<p>partners and stakeholders regarding new developments in research, politics, and co-design work in the FEAST living labs. To amplify the voices of those living and working in FEAST cities.</p>	<p>Five internal webinars in the past 12 months, one public Policy Chat, and two Hackathon dissemination webinar.</p>
<p>Social Media</p>	<p>To reach a wide, targeted audience, maximizing the impact and successful exploitation of project results.</p>	<p>LinkedIn started in July 2022 – Ongoing: Weekly posting (minimum one post per week) of current topics and project updates. YouTube started in October 2022 – updated frequently, according to demand. X (Twitter) started in March 2023 – stopped posting in May 2024.</p>
<p>Animation, animated infographics</p>	<p>To present a simplified, short, and more accessible presentation of FEAST updates and messages.</p>	<p>Started in October 2022 – Ongoing: Frequency according to demand</p>

	Activity	Objective of activity	State of implementation & current status
DISSEMINATION	Open access and open science	To make FEAST research outputs and results FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable).	First publication published in November 2022 – Ongoing: As soon as they can be made public.
	Hands-on workshops	To work together with external groups on relevant topics.	Ongoing
	Fairs, community talks and conferences	To inform external groups about FEAST subjects related to food, health and/or sustainability at specific events.	First conference participation in September 2022 - Ongoing: continuous review of relevant events and communication with FEAST partners about opportunities to participate. Preparation and sharing monthly internal DEC newsletter with upcoming conferences and dissemination opportunities
EXPLOITATION	Zenodo	To make FEAST's data and deliverables open and accessible	Started in June 2023 – Ongoing: Upload of documents as soon as they can be made public.
	EOSC Marketplace	To promote FEAST outputs	Not started yet
	Git-Repositories	To document the software developed within FEAST and make it open source.	Started in January 2025 – Ongoing, accessible here: https://github.com/FEAST-simulation-library
	Replicator cities	To transfer methods and results to follower cities.	Started in March 2025 – Kickoff Replication Programm with nine replication cities, October 2025
	Hackathons	To develop new ideas and services for specific food challenges.	Started in May 2023 – Ongoing: Five during the project period Hackathon events are finished, prototypes are complete, currently working on dissemination and exploitation of results.
	Summer schools	To train and educate young people. (1) school pupils and (2) university students.	Process started in March 2025 - Ongoing: First Summer School, September 2025

Introduction

The Multi Actor Approach (MAA), as defined by the Horizon Europe - Work Programme 2023-2024¹, is at the core of FEAST's approach to ensure that all food system actors are empowered to support the just transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour. Following a trans- and interdisciplinary logic of research and innovation, the project consortium leverages nested co-creation on multiple levels. This is achieved via collaboration with 35 partners from 15 European Countries with complementary skills, knowledge and competencies representing the food system. FEAST messages are visible during and beyond the lifetime of the project. The overall DEC framework provides guidance for partners communicating through various means including media, internet, and publications. The strategic plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication was presented in the first version of the DEC plan (see Figure 1). Dissemination and exploitation activities are designed to ensure that the results achieved meet FEAST's objectives and maximise the project's overall impact.

Figure 1 Strategic plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities in FEAST

Dissemination, exploitation and communication are distinct but interlinked concepts. FEAST's DEC activities are designed based on the European Commission's templates² to support a paradigm shift to food systems that are fairer, healthier, and more environmentally friendly for all actors (primary production to consumption), particularly vulnerable groups. All DEC activities are being designed in an inclusive and evidence-based way to support FEAST's pathways to impact.

The overarching objective of FEAST's DEC activities is to raise levels of awareness of food system actors, including citizens, about transitions towards healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour.

More specific objectives include:

- To create and **communicate** content to boost the visibility and support engagement of food and health system stakeholders (including media and public) with FEAST objectives and

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-9-food-bioeconomy-natural-resources-agriculture-and-environment_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf#page=21 (page 21 – 23, accessed on 28.12.2023)

² https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-dissemination-and-exploitation_en and https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en (both accessed on 5.11.2022)

activities, for both traditional media (brochures, booklets, etc.) and digital media (i.e., website, electronic newsletters, podcasts).

- To **disseminate** project results to internal and external target audiences through scientific and other channels (i.e., community talks, workshops) at European and local levels.
- To utilise project results and improve the transfer of technical and scientific knowledge outside the core consortium to facilitate **exploitation** of results.

These objectives will be delivered through a wide range of activities as outlined in Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 in section 1.

1 Overview of FEAST's DEC Activities

The following section provides an overview of the planned and ongoing DEC activities in FEAST. Section 2.3 provides more concrete information and details of the activities and outputs FEAST has achieved between M6-M35.

1.1.1 FEAST Communication Activities

FEAST's communication activities aim to inform, promote, and communicate FEAST activities and results to relevant actors across the food system (Figure 2):

Figure 2 FEAST communication activities

Table 3 State of implementation of FEAST's communication activities

	Activity	Objective of activity	State of implementation & current status
COMMUNICATION	Website	To give FEAST web visibility, provide further background information and updates on project progress.	Started in July 2022 Ongoing: Main FEAST pages include 12 distinct pages, linking to 75 subpages.
	Internal newsletter	To inform FEAST partners about updates within the WPs as well as updates on important external news.	Started: First release January 2023 – Ongoing: Every quarter, four times per year.
	External newsletter	To inform FEAST newsletter subscribers about updates from FEAST.	Started: First release April 2023 – Ongoing: Every six months, twice per year. Overview of the past newsletter: Press Corner FEAST Three more external newsletters have been sent out in the last 12 months.
	Press releases	To update target audiences on FEAST outputs through journalists and mainstream media	Started: First release August 2022 – Ongoing: At irregular intervals, but as soon as there is something to report to the press. Three press releases have been issued in the past 12 months.
	Brochures, booklets, flyer	To provide high-quality information about FEAST and its WPs through printed materials.	Started: August 2022 Ongoing: Frequency according to demand. The FEAST highlight brochure is a summary of project highlights which is published once a year in October. The first edition was published in October 2023. <i>First Year Highlights, 2022/23</i> <i>Second Year Highlights, 2023/24</i> A FEAST flyer was created for conferences and dissemination events. <i>It provides a brief overview of the project.</i>

		<i>Resources FEAST</i>
Meetings, webinars, dialogs and workshops, podcasts	To inform and support FEAST partners and stakeholders regarding new developments in research, politics and co-design work in the FEAST living labs. To amplify the voices of those living and working in FEAST cities.	<p>Started: August 2022</p> <p>Ongoing: Frequency according to demand</p> <p>2024/2025: Five internal webinars in the past 12 months, one public Policy Chat and two Hackathon dissemination webinars (Milan and London).</p>
Social Media	To reach a wide, targeted audience, maximizing the impact and successful exploitation of project results.	<p>Started: LinkedIn – July 2022</p> <p>Ongoing: Weekly posting (minimum one post per week) of current topics and project updates.</p> <p>YouTube started in October 2022 – updated frequently, according to demand and available material.</p> <p>X (Twitter) started in March 2023 – stopped posting in May 2024.</p>
Animation, animated infographics	To present a simplified, short and more accessible presentation of FEAST updates and messages.	<p>Started: October 2022</p> <p>Ongoing: Frequency according to demand</p>

1.1.2 FEAST Dissemination Activities

FEAST's dissemination activities aim to make FEAST results public to ensure our results can be adopted by relevant food system actors (Figure 3):

Figure 3 FEAST dissemination activities

Table 4 State of implementation of FEAST's dissemination activities

Activity	Objective of activity	State of implementation & current status
Open access and open science	To make FEAST research outputs and results FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable).	Started: First publication published in November 2022 Ongoing: As soon as they can be made public.
Hands-on workshops	To work together with external groups on relevant topics.	Ongoing
Fairs, community talks and conferences	To inform external groups about FEAST subjects related to food, health and/or sustainability at specific events.	Started: First conference participation in September 2022 Ongoing: continuous review of relevant events and communication with FEAST partners about opportunities to participate. Monthly internal DEC newsletter with upcoming conferences and dissemination opportunities.

1.1.3 FEAST Exploitation Activities

FEAST's exploitation activities aim to support relevant actors to make concrete use of FEAST results (Figure 4):

Figure 4 FEAST exploitation activities

Table 5 State of implementation of FEAST's exploitation activities

Activity	Objective of activity	State of implementation & current status
Zenodo	To make FEAST's data and deliverables open and accessible	Started: June 2023 Ongoing: Upload of documents as soon as they can be made public.
EOSC Marketplace	To promote FEAST outputs	Not started yet
Git-Repositories	To document the software developed within FEAST and make it open source.	Started: April 2025 Ongoing: WP6 started to upload code and data.
Replicator cities	To transfer methods and results to follower cities.	Started: March 2025 Ongoing: Replication Programme Kick Off October 2025
Hackathons	To develop new ideas and services for specific food challenges. Five Hackathons during the project period	Started: May 2023 Ended: February 2025 State: Working on finalizing the prototypes and making results available

Summer schools	To train and educate young people. (1) school pupils and (2) university students.	First Summer School, September 2025
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2 Methodology: Designing and implementing DEC activities

FEAST's methodology for DEC activities involves five steps (identify target audience and messages, select tools, plan and implement activities) in a continuous loop, including a subloop between steps 1 and 2, with updates planned yearly (Figure 5):

Figure 5 FEAST methodology for DEC activities

For each of the groups in the food supply chain, specific decisions must be made during the course of the project for which messages are being sent, with which tools, and when activities will take place. This is a continuous process with the individual activities being reviewed in terms of their effectiveness in reaching our intended audience and they are adjusted if necessary.

2.1 Target Groups

Figure 6 illustrates how FEAST accounts for, works with and impacts Europe's food system and its actors. Here, the food system is defined as "all the elements (environment, people, inputs, processes, infrastructure, institutions) and activities that relate to the pre-production, production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food and the outputs of these activities, including socioeconomic and environmental outcomes"³ (see Annex 2 for a description of FEAST WPs).

Figure 6 How FEAST will account for, work with and impact the food system and its actors.

FEAST partners can be broadly classified as being from higher education & research, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), public bodies and private companies (see Table 6). Considering the size of the consortium, we have developed a DEC strategy that takes into account the different

DEC needs of the different types of partners in the consortium so that they can effectively reach their intended audiences (e.g. ensuring that the materials are available in different languages, ensuring that different approaches are designed to communicate with different types of vulnerable groups). Additionally, given the size of our consortium, we also work to ensure effective communications to our partners. Moreover, the consortium size and the FEAST activities and ambitions are already resulting in project-related partnerships that are leading to third-party stakeholders in the FEAST DEC strategy. In the following sections, the internal and external target groups are explained in more detail.

Table 6 FEAST's MAA approach – partner type and partner's name

Partner Type	Partners name
Higher education & research – 14 in total	University of Heidelberg, NCSR “Demokritos”, Roskilde University, Sciensano, University College Cork, Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture, Institut de Recherche Pour Le Development, Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, Università degli Studi di Scienze Gastronomiche, University of Graz, Instituto Politecnico de Viana de Castelo, University of Lodz, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau
NGOs – 10 in total	EuroHealthNet, EAT Foundation, Arete, Ökosoziales Forum Österreich & Europa, ICLEI Europe, Louis Bolk Institute, open science for open societies, Good Food Oxfordshire, Leuven2030, OpenDot
Public bodies – 9 in total	Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alto Minho, Commune d'Avignon, Opshtina Prilep, Municipality of Sitia, LEADER-Region Weinviertel Donauraum, City of Gent, Azienda USL Toscana, Cork City, Guldborgsund Municipality
Private companies – 2 in total	myLabel, Susmetro

2.1.1 Internal Target Groups

BOX Nr. 1 - Definition of internal target groups

By internal target group we mean the project team, employees at the project partners institutions and people that can directly be involved in FEAST research activities. Partner projects in which FEAST project partners are involved fall into the category of external groups.

FEAST has two broad categories of internal groups within our partner organisations:

Tier 1: individuals at FEAST partner organisations directly involved with FEAST

Tier 2: individuals at FEAST partner organisations not directly involved with FEAST

FEAST partners were asked which internal target groups/audiences were most important for them to effectively communicate FEAST outputs to and who could benefit from the project's insights; the results are highlighted in Table 7:

Table 7 Internal target groups/audience mentioned by the FEASTs partners

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	University researchers, academic staff, students, team colleagues, alumni, visiting professors, institutional climate change center, and trans-academic research manager
NGOs	Farmer and Business Association, Politicians, Administration Officers, Universities, internal team members, partners from municipalities, tech people, health specialists, makers and designers
Public bodies	Management of the city, municipal and regional administration, national level (Ministries and government), politicians (to allocate money), schools, caretakers, the press, producers of local food and LLs from Prilep, Gent, Oxfordshire, and Leuven
Private companies	Engaged people in associations, people conscious of the planet, jobless people, independent NGOs, brands, labels, start-ups, and retailers

2.1.2 External Target Groups

BOX Nr. 2 – Definition of external target groups

External target groups of FEAST are those not falling within internal target groups.

Given FEAST's outreach to micro, meso and macro levels of the food system (Figure 6 and Table 7), there is a requirement to communicate with a variety of external audiences to ensure effective dissemination of the knowledge and insights coming from the project and facilitate the scaling of FEAST's outputs across Europe as highlighted in Table 8.

Table 8 FEAST External target groups of FEAST and their corresponding levels

Level	Target group categories and examples
Macro	<p>Representative bodies (e.g. CGIAR, EU Food Policy Forum)</p> <p>Intergovernmental organisations (e.g. WHO, UN bodies)</p> <p>Policy makers (e.g. EU, national)</p>
Meso	<p>Healthcare professionals (e.g. pediatricians, those working on CVD/NCDs)</p> <p>Food producers (e.g. farmers (advocacy groups), companies producing processed foods)</p> <p>Food-related businesses (e.g. retailers, distributors LL communities, local food councils)</p>
Micro	<p>Food producers (e.g. farmers (individual))</p> <p>Other entities (e.g. Academics/Researchers, NGOs working with vulnerable groups)</p>

Within the different levels of the food system, there are also certain external target groups that are a priority for FEAST partners to communicate with (Table 9):

Table 9 External target groups/audience mentioned by FEAST's partners

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	<p>Cluster academic: Academic audiences, scientific journals, audience during external lectures, conferences</p> <p>Cluster policy: Policy makers and interest groups (Chamber of Agriculture, city administration, politicians interested in the topic), public bodies like municipalities regions states and the EU</p> <p>Vulnerable groups: Children and youth, elderly, people with type 2 diabetes, managers of care homes</p> <p>Society: Civil society organizations (food coops), social economy actors (innovative cooperative solutions); local communities, CoLabs, citizens of the municipality</p> <p>Food sector: farmers, food producers, retailers, wholesalers, food service industry people</p> <p>Media: Local media and newspaper, press companies communities citizens NGOs, local radio, social media</p>
NGOs	Our NGOs named researchers and Universities, politicians at national government, municipality, local and national media, farmers and citizens.
Public bodies	Municipalities and local authority, school communities (teachers, students, parents, etc.), small farmers and fishermen (also their

	associations), citizen, groups related to policies (health authorities, social work), Urban Lab partners and network of NGOs.
Private companies	Municipalities, urban planners and individuals

2.2 Design of Target Messages

The design and delivery of FEAST's messages aim to ensure that they align with FEAST's Theory of Change (Section 2.2.1 - Table 10) and are framed under FEAST's Key Messages (Section 2.2.2) and Unique Selling Points (Section 2.2.3). In addition to this, the different interests and priorities of FEAST's target internal and external audiences are taken into account to ensure that FEAST outputs are framed into messages that align with the language (i.e. jargon and non-jargon), communication modalities and priorities of stakeholders across the food system.

2.2.1 FEAST's Theory of Change

FEAST's goal is to transform food systems to ensure all individuals can easily eat a healthier and more sustainable diet. Achieving this goal requires working across the micro, meso and macro levels of food systems and supporting different actors to deliver impact. Table 10 outlines FEAST's theory of change which underpins all actions within the project as well as the design of FEAST's DEC activities, all of which are guided by our Theory of Change-informed Key Messages (Section 2.2.2) and Unique Selling Points (Section 2.2.3).

Table 10 FEAST target groups, outcomes and impacts

Target Groups	Outcomes	Impacts
<p><u>Micro Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU citizens, including diverse vulnerable groups. - Non-governmental, consumer, community and patient organisations. - SMEs. - Small farmers. <p><u>Meso Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food Environment. - Provincial/Municipal/Local authorities. - Large food industry (producers, distributors, retailers). - Hospitality/Catering. - Healthcare providers. 	<p><u>Micro Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals, especially vulnerable groups, have more knowledge on what constitutes healthier and more sustainable diets; the knowledge is put into action by these individuals adopting healthier and more sustainable dietary choices; less food insecurity; medium to long-term we will see a reduction in NCDs. <p><u>Meso Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food environments that support healthier and more sustainable diets - Businesses: fewer unhealthy and unsustainably produced dietary products on offer; increase in 	<p><u>Scientific</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advancing the state of the art to improve knowledge and understanding of the factors (barriers and facilitators), across the micro-, meso- and macro-levels of the food system influencing the dietary behaviours of different target groups (in particular, vulnerable groups) across Europe. <p><u>Social</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health: Decreased NCD burden; reduced health inequalities; decreased need for public sector expenditure (especially healthcare) stemming from NCDs.

<p>- Education system.</p> <p>Macro Level</p> <p>- National Authorities.</p> <p>- EU Commission & policymakers.</p>	<p>affordable, local, healthier and more sustainably produced products on offer;</p> <p>--Institutions: increased availability and use of healthier and more sustainable meal options.</p> <p>Macro Level</p> <p>- Increased adoption of food and health policy interventions at National and EU levels that support the just transition to healthier and more sustainable diets by all stakeholders in the food system.</p>	<p>- Environment: Decreased environmental impact of the food system.</p> <p>- Economy: Improved opportunities and livelihoods for small farmers and food SMEs.</p> <p>Policy</p> <p>Stronger scientific basis to inform the design and implementation of evidence-based policies by policymakers and Member States to build 'Win-Win-Win-Win' food systems that will empower individuals to adopt healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours.</p>
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2.2.2 Key Messages

Clear messages are important for good communication. They need to convey the content and goals of the project while also appealing to various target groups. The following key messages are based on FEAST's Theory of Change and are used to inform DEC activities for different target groups.

An update to our first key message was done in the past 12 months. To ensure we are targeting every person living in Europe and not just European citizens or individuals who identify as 'European', as well as highlighting that they should be able to easily access a diet that is delicious, healthier and more sustainable.

BOX Nr. 3 – FEAST's top level key messages

First key message

FEAST aims to make it easy for every European to eat a healthy and sustainable diet.

Update of the first key message

FEAST aims to make it easy for every person in Europe to eat a delicious, healthier and more sustainable diet.

Second key message

FEAST aims to catalyse Europe's just transition to a 'Win-Win-Win-Win' food system that sees major gains for people, the planet, and the public and private sectors.

Third key message

FEAST aims to ensure the EU's policies actually walk the walk, not just talk the talk.

2.2.3 FEAST's Unique Selling Points (USP)

In consultation with our project partners, we aimed to identify their perspectives on FEAST's key unique selling points (USPs), which are summarised in Table 11 below:

Table 11 *Project Unique Selling Points mentioned by the FEASTs partners*

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	Partners from higher education & research see the USP in the broad applicable approach of FEAST; the integrated and inclusive approach to food; health and environment to tackle the challenge of healthy and sustainable food systems; engagement with the living labs; the overall systems based solutions to food system challenges and the transition to Win-Win-Win-Win food systems.
NGOs	NGOs mentioned personal discussions, multi-actor approach and improved wellbeing of people.
Public bodies	Affordable food for vulnerable groups; practical impact; public cooperation on promotion of healthy food (e.g. in schools); health and sustainability through food is achievable for ALL; the international, integral & holistic perspective which leads again to the transition to Win-Win-Win-Win food systems.
Private companies	Actual change in lives with real life solutions backed by science leading to impact, practical & trustful food systems.

Building on the USPs identified by partners, DEC activities highlight a core mechanism through which FEAST will embed co-ownership: FEAST's 'living labs'- user-focused experimental environment in which municipalities, end-users (citizens) and stakeholders are supported to co-create innovative solutions in real-world settings. Figure 7 displays the FEAST living lab network, associated sites and food regions. FEAST's associated large city living labs provide the ideal avenue for identifying and recruiting vulnerable populations for our co-creation actions.

Living Lab spotlights—as blogs and as part of social media campaigns—center co-creation processes in varied local contexts. To ensure representation across the EU, FEAST's living labs include rural areas, small/medium cities, and associated large city living labs according to a specific typology of food systems that cover aspects including regional diets, food production systems, and welfare systems (i.e., Beveridge/Bismarckian healthcare systems) characteristics. This diversity of location and situation are reflected in our communication materials. Furthermore, non-recurrent opportunities, such as the featuring of a city on an external podcast or other multi-media product, are being taken advantage of when they arise.

Figure 7 FEAST's Food regions and living labs

2.3 Selecting Tools, Planning & Implementing Activities

As outlined in Figure 1, FEAST has several general communication channels, including FEAST's website, internal and external newsletters, social media channels like LinkedIn and YouTube (digital channels), as well as brochures, booklets, and flyers (printed media) (Section 2.3.3). The aim of using different channels and tools is to reach a broad audience based on their preference for receiving material. To this end, we consulted for the development of our first DEC plan with our project partners to understand preferred communication channels for both internal and external target audiences (Sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2).

In the following section examples are given to show activities FEAST has undertaken from M6-M17 and M18-M35 linked to the use of:

- FEAST's key messages for different DEC activities
- Different channels to reach our internal and external target audiences
- FEAST's existing and newly created communication and dissemination materials
- To support exploitation of FEAST's outputs

2.3.1 DEC Approaches for Internal Audiences

For the development of the first DEC plan, FEAST partners were asked which communication media they currently use for internal communication. The corresponding tools for internal project communication were derived from the insights garnered from the survey (Section 2.3.3).

To date, the following channels have been established for DEC activities targeting internal audiences:

- Members of the DEC working group attended bi-weekly WP meetings in the first 24 months and reported on their DEC-related activities. Furthermore, this activity was used to evaluate the needs of the individual WPs (listening to their needs). From month 25 on, the WP8 meeting frequency has been changed to once a month. The frequency of the meetings was modified due to the fact that the team had a comprehensive understanding of all internal processes, thereby making the bi-weekly meetings unnecessary.
- File sharing and internal communication with Teams and SharePoint, including:
 - separate channels for each WP
 - a channel where all recordings for the internal webinars, consortium meetings, hackathons, and policy chats are available
 - a channel related to ethics, sharing general resources related to ethics
- Email lists for internal communication:
 - **Admin email list** - Membership: All participants involved in FEAST, including admin staff, are included in this list and it is used to communicate updates on administrative issues
 - **Research email list** – Membership: Generally non-admin staff are included in this list (e.g. both academic and non-academic FEASTies)
 - **Methods email list** - Membership: Currently, only WP and task leads as well as living lab (LL) academic partners are included in this list. Junior researchers and any other FEAST member can 'opt-in' to join this list. The purpose of this list is to coordinate and harmonise methods across FEAST WPs and to “scientifically” discuss relevant political or policy aspects. Anyone in this list can post, and the focus is on the methods used in the studies being conducted within FEAST. The methods group can also serve as a place for junior researchers to learn and share.
 - **Living Lab email list** – People active in the Living Lab actions. Posting: anyone part of this list can post and it is meant for general updates including news from the Living Labs.
 - **DEC email list** – This new email list was introduced in January 2025. WP leads receive a monthly DEC email with upcoming and potential dissemination opportunities. They forward it to suitable partners in their work package.
- A Quarterly internal email newsletter is used to communicate the project’s progress, present partner profiles, or highlight upcoming conferences and relevant publications.
- Internal webinars on policy to inform and support FEAST partners to navigate developments in research, politics and ground work at the living labs. EuroHealthNet, lead of WP7 (Policy dialogues to inform food system governance), initiated the first series of internal webinars called “FEAST Policy Chat” with the following format:
 - Online event of 1-1.5 hours held on a regular basis.
 - Start of the event, WP7 representatives present two or three of the main policy developments that have occurred between M6-M17 and M18-35.
 - Q&A session and conclusion

Table 12 shows the webinars already held on policy chats and other topics. The purpose of these webinars is to increase the internal exchange of knowledge, create stronger linkages between WPs as they relate to policy aspects and to develop concepts for external webinars.

Table 12 FEAST internal webinars already held

Nr.	Title	Brief description of the webinar	Length	Date
1	1 st training session for living labs Held by OpenDot	Human Centered Design and Co-Design. Practical guide on how to find meaningful solutions based on user needs.	1 hour 23 minutes	13.02. 2023
2	2 nd training session for living labs Held by OpenDot	From Brief to Concept: make your ideas "cubic"- Practical guide on how to trigger creativity in participatory processes.	1 hour 24 minutes	27.02. 2023
3	3 rd training session for living labs Held by OpenDot	From Concept to Prototypes. How to create a concrete way to test your ideas in the field.	1 hour 26 minutes	13.03. 2023
4	1 st Policy Chat Meeting Held by EuroHealthNet	Introduction to the structure of the meetings. A common target: healthier and more sustainable food systems.	1 hour	17.03. 2023
5	Open Research Europe - FEAST, PLAN'EAT and SWICHT Held by F1000 (external)	Introduction to Open Research Europe (ORE) by F1000, how to publish on ORE. What is Open Diamond, what are the FAIR data principles, data sharing and types of articles in ORE.	1 hour	12.05. 2022
6	2 nd Policy Chat Meeting Held by EuroHealthNet	Food security	54 minutes	02.06. 2023
7	3 th Policy Chat – SFS Held by EuroHealthNet	End () of the Sustainable Food System policy?	57 minutes	24.10. 2023
8	1st webinar - FEAST reporting period Held by University of Heidelberg	Processes linked with reporting - including the completion of time sheets, signing into the EU portal and filling out the relevant forms on the Horizon Europe portal.	49 minutes	28.11. 2023
9	1 st WP2 Data Processors Seminar	Data Processing (DP) meeting for the EU survey data	1.50 hours	05.02. 2024
10	2 nd WP2 Data Processors Seminar	Data Processing (DP) meeting for the EU survey data	1.06 hours	04.03. 2024
11	WP8 – Gender mainstreaming webinar - part 1	Introduction on gender mainstreaming tools by Aleksandra Różalska from University of Łódź.	1.30 hours	11.09. 2024

12	WP8 – Gender - Intersectionality webinar - part 2	Introduction on intersectionality by Aleksandra Różalska from University of Łódź.	1.30 hours	23.10. 2024
13	WP8 – Gender - Impact assessment – part 3	Introduction on impact assessment by Aleksandra Różalska from University of Łódź.	1.30 hours	08.01. 2025
14	4 th Policy Chat on EU Vision for Agriculture and Food	The European Commission has just released its Vision on the future of Food and Agriculture. This document is pivotal because it defines the direction of EU policies in the coming years.	1.23 hours	06.03. 2025
15	WP6 – Spatial distribution of WP2 survey data	The team was presented with an analysis of the WP2 survey data. The primary focus of the webinar was on the spatial distribution of WP2 data.	36 minutes	24.04. 2025
16	WP8 – Toolkit on behaviour change techniques	Introduction on drivers, barriers and techniques for behavior change	29 minutes	20.05. 2025

2.3.2 DEC Approaches for External Audiences

FEAST partners were also asked in the survey about their preferred communication channels with external actors. Suggestions included:

- Informal talks, meetings, calls, face-to-face talks, direct conversation, seminars
- Department-owned email lists for employees
- Website and intranet
- Newsletter articles at the homepage and newsletter with MailChimp
- Podcasts
- Newspaper and press
- Google docs for writing articles
- Tools: Teams, Slack, WhatsApp, OneDrive, Outlook, Canva
- Social media: LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Instagram, Facebook

The updates for the external audiences are linked with the general DEC approaches, which can be seen in Section 2.3.3.

2.3.3 General DEC Approaches

To maximise the effectiveness and efficiency of FEAST's DEC activities, we will design and utilise FEAST-specific DEC approaches, which are described in the sections below. In addition to this and to fully capitalise on network effects, FEAST also uses the existing channels available to FEAST partners (Table 13).

Table 13 External communication channels mentioned by the FEASTs partners

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	Website, press release, and email Social media: LinkedIn, YouTube, X (Twitter), Facebook, Instagram, Podcasts Print: Posters, leaflets, banners
NGOs	Email for press release and website Social media: LinkedIn, YouTube
Public bodies	Institutional website, emails, and stakeholder events Social media: Facebook, YouTube, X (Twitter), Instagram
Private companies	PR and LinkedIn

2.3.3.1 Project Websites

2.3.3.1.1 FEAST's Project Website

To give FEAST online visibility, the domain www.feast2030.eu has been reserved for the project over the next eight years – the five years of the project and three years following the conclusion of the project. The FEAST website will be continuously developed and will receive regular updates and upgrades to its functionalities. The first version of the website was published on July 24, 2022, coinciding with the creation of the [FEAST LinkedIn group](#).

The technical implementation is realized with the open-source content management system Drupal (<https://www.drupal.org/>). Drupal provides the balance between powerful functionality out of the box and the flexibility to make it your own.

Since the release of the first version of the website, there have been several updates to the functionalities.

The website includes the following elements at the moment:

- Home (Landing page)
- Project
 - About – gives an overview of FEAST's objectives
 - Activity areas - focusing on WP activities, including subpages for each WP (see Table 14)
 - Research Activities – focusing on current and upcoming activities. Provides details about the hackathons, myLabel trial and WP surveys.

- Living Labs
 - Overview – gives an overview of Living Lab activities and local food challenges
 - Introduction – gives an overview of FEAST's food regions and living lab sites, including subpages for each living lab
- Resources – area where FEAST material is made available for download
- Knowledge Corner –
 - News – Blog posts on relevant topics related to FEAST's research topic, discuss and present new studies on the topics that FEAST addresses, and present the work of our research partners, as well as our municipal partners.
 - FEAST glossary - glossary of terms relevant for FEAST's research activities
- Contact – information on how to get in contact with FEAST.

In the second development phase of the FEAST website, the following pages had been added:

- Project
 - Advisory Board – introducing our external Research and Innovation Advisory Board
- Activities
 - FEAST Webinars – An overview of our public webinars
 - Community of Practice (for Food & Health – introduces the CoP concept and objectives
 - Hack For Food Hack For Good – a landing page for the FEAST hackathon events with links to each hackathon as a separate event page
 - Summer School – event page with details for participants
 - Replication Programme – overview of the FEAST replication programme
- Knowledge Corner
 - Podcasts – embedded podcasts from the project or external podcasts where FEAST consortium members have been invited as guests
 - Videos – a gallery with external video recordings from conferences, webinars or other dissemination events where FEAST consortium members took part
- Press Corner – area with links to our press releases as well as external newsletters

The monitoring of the FEAST website usage clearly demonstrates that providing constant new and relevant content not only makes the website interesting for visitors, it also brings a better ranking on search engines like google and bing.

Figure 8 shows a screenshot of the HOME landing page. The page aggregates content from the subpages to display the most relevant and latest content directly when entering the FEAST website. It balances dynamic content like news and events with more static content like the Living Lab profile pages.

Figure 8

Screenshot of the FEAST website landing page - Home (Accessed on 10.05.2025)

Figure 9 shows a screenshot of the page about *FEAST's hackathons* "Hack for Food Hack for Good". The page is an example of how activities and events are structured. It provides information about the aim of the hackathons, the formats, and how to participate in them.

The screenshot shows the FEAST website's 'Hack for Food, Hack for Good' page. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Home, Project, Activities, Living Labs, Resources, and Knowledge Corner. The main header features the FEAST logo and the title 'Hack for Food, Hack for Good' on a colorful background. Below the header, the page is divided into several sections:

- Hackathons in Europe create social impact solutions for healthier and more sustainable diets:** This section includes a paragraph explaining that the 'Hack for Food Hack for Good' series is organized by FEAST partner OpenDot, a Milan-based fab lab. It also describes the format as a short, timed, competitive event where teams work together to solve challenges. A photograph of fresh produce in a market basket is included.
- Why Hackathons?:** This section explains that hackathons offer a transdisciplinary environment for problem-solving and innovation. It notes that winners receive support and mentorship from OpenDot. A photograph shows a group of people collaborating around a table with laptops.
- Final event in Copenhagen:** This section announces the final event in March 2025, organized by OpenDot at Copenhagen Business School. It mentions that winners of previous hackathons will present their solutions to transform Europe's food value chain. A photograph shows beer being brewed in large tanks.
- Read about our previous events:** This section lists past events with their dates and locations: Berlin, Germany (November 2024), Kaunas, Lithuania (September 2024), London, England (February 2024), and Milan, Italy (May 2023). A collage of images representing these cities and their flags is shown.

Figure 9 Screenshot of the FEAST website, Hackathon overview page (Accessed on 10.06.2025)

Figure 10 is a screenshot of the Knowledge Corner. Articles posted here are linked to our social media channels. The article authors are FEAST partners from all domains who provide a variety of insights related to the project's objectives. At the time of writing the report (June 2025), 31 blog posts had been published in FEAST's Knowledge Corner. Our aim is to publish more than 50 blog posts by the end of the project.

Figure 10 Screenshot of the FEAST Knowledge Corner (Accessed on 18.06.2025)

Figure 11 is an example screenshot of the Living Lab subpage of our partner Guldborgsund (first release). Visitors get detailed information about the local food challenges, links to relevant videos on the FEAST YouTube channel and frequently asked questions to the LL. Table 14 provides an overview of the living lab sites and subpages.

Country: Denmark

Region/City: Guldborgsund Municipality

Food region: Scandinavian group

Type: Rural

Figure 11 Screenshot of the FEAST Living Lab subpage, Guldborgsund (Accessed on 27.11.2022)

Figure 12 shows the LL profile pages with the updates made in 2024, including additional local information like target groups, links to local press clippings from national media, and testimonials from their stakeholders. This allows visitors to filter options according to their interests.

Country: Denmark

Food Region: Scandinavian

Type: Rural

Target Group: Schools
Children
Parents

Figure 12 Screenshot of the FEAST Living Lab subpage, Guldborgsund (Accessed on 10.06.2025)

Table 14 Links to FEAST's Living Labs site pages

Title and Link to Living Lab site	Subtitel of the site (Living Lab message)
<i>Avignon FEAST Living Lab</i>	Healthy food education and meals in Avignon schools
<i>CIM Alto Minho FEAST Living Lab</i>	Transitioning to healthier and more sustainable food systems in Alto Minho's school canteens Children inspire change
<i>Ghent FEAST Living Lab</i>	Provide sustainable food accessible to all
<i>Guldborgsund FEAST Living Lab</i>	School Food and Nutrition Education in Guldborgsund Municipality
<i>LEADER Weinregion Donauviertel FEAST Living Lab</i>	Enhance the food options provided at the canteens of manufacturing and service companies
<i>Leuven FEAST Living Lab</i>	Healthy and sustainable diets for vulnerable groups - through digital platforms and communication
<i>Senior-WIGOR Day Care Centre FEAST Living Lab</i>	Elderly people have very specific dietary and nutritional needs
<i>Oxfordshire FEAST Living Lab</i>	Understanding and exploring ways to support healthy and sustainable diets in vulnerable groups in Oxfordshire
<i>Prilep FEAST Living Lab</i>	Promoting and preserving traditional and sustainable diets
<i>Rotterdam Boulevard Zuid FEAST Living Lab</i>	Due to a partner change (Cork is replacing Rotterdam); the page for Rotterdam on the FEAST site was deactivated and is not online anymore.
<i>Tuscany Region FEAST Living Lab</i>	A healthy and conscious approach towards food and nutrition
<i>Sitia (Greek Σητεία) FEAST Living Lab</i>	Ensure the long-term sustainability of Sitia olive oil
<i>Cork a FEAST Living Lab</i>	As a Living Lab, Cork City is co-creating and implementing a Sustainable and Healthy Food Strategy for the city

The development of the website is a continuous process for communicating and disseminating project outputs, living lab actions, news, blog posts from presentations, publications, and events.

Table 15 shows the web analytics for the two reporting periods; notable insights are:

- The site **nearly doubled** in both visits and page views.
- Traffic from **search engines and external websites** grew the most significantly.
- Downloads (both total and unique) experienced a **significant increase** of over **750%**.

- Despite growth in all channels, the share of **social network traffic declined** from 7% to 4%.

Table 15 Web Analytics Overview: Update 01 (24.07.2022 – 2023.11.30) vs. Update 02 (2023.12.01 – 2025.05.31)

Metric	Update 01	Update 02	% Change
Total Website Visits	9,782	19,382	+98%
– Direct Entries	6,121	10,610	+73%
– From Search Engines	2,246	6,269	+179%
– From Other Websites	665	1,736	+161%
– From Social Networks	650	714	+10%
Avg. Website Visits/Month	575	1,140	
Total Page Views	22,855	45,382	+100%
Avg. Page Views/Month	1,344	2,670	
Unique Page Views	18,298	36,813	+101%
Total Downloads	144	1,257	+773%
Unique Downloads	135	1,149	+751%

2.3.3.1.2 FEAST's Partner Websites

Each FEAST partner has been asked to refer to FEAST on their websites and to describe the FEAST activities they are mainly involved in (see Figure 13, an image of the EuroHealthNet's website). Table 16 presents a list of the FEAST WP lead organisation websites and links to the FEAST subpages on their websites.

Table 16 FEAST WP lead organisation websites and link to FEAST

Partner	Hyperlink
University of Heidelberg (Lead: WP1, 5 and 9)	https://www.uni-heidelberg.de/en <i>FEAST on the HIGH website</i>
EuroHealthNet (Lead: WP7)	https://eurohealthnet.eu <i>FEAST on the EuroHealthNet website</i>
Sciensano (Lead: WP3)	https://www.sciensano.be/en <i>FEAST on the Sciensano website</i>
ICLEI Europe (Lead: WP4)	https://iclei-europe.org <i>FEAST on the ICLEI website</i>
Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture (Lead: WP6)	https://www.inrae.fr <i>FEAST on the INRAE website</i>
open science for open societies (Lead: WP8)	https://os4os.org/en <i>FEAST on the os4os website</i>
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (Lead: WP2)	https://www.santannapisa.it/en <i>FEAST on the SSA website</i>

Partners with their own newsletters and blogs are also looking for opportunities to highlight their connection with FEAST in order to foster engagement, interest, and participation among their target internal and external audiences, thus enhancing the project's visibility.

Figure 13 Partners are encouraged to feature FEAST on their organisational web pages, as illustrated by this image of the EuroHealthNet's website (Accessed on 15.11.2023).

Each partner has internal guidelines on how projects should be presented on their own websites as well as project-specific requirements resulting from FEAST. To ensure that FEAST content is widely disseminated, the following best practices are recommended for our partners:

- if possible, the FEAST key messages should be mentioned
- integrate a link to the FEAST website www.feast2030.eu
- integrate links to FEAST's social media channels

These measures ensure that interested visitors are provided with further information and that the results are visible.

2.3.3.2 Press Work

Press releases for newsworthy elements linked to FEAST (including important outputs, innovations and resources) are being prepared regularly. The FEAST DEC team is reaching out to local and European level media to present them with these newsworthy elements from FEAST while also supporting dissemination of their material that is relevant to FEAST's objectives. Furthermore, all project partners, in particular our living lab cities and communities, share project news of local significance with local and national contacts.

To date, FEAST has released five press releases; information on these can be found in the Press Corner of the FEAST website [Press Corner | FEAST](#)

The Press Corner of the FEAST website serves as a central hub for media engagement and communication. It provides direct contact details for Dr. Anant Jani, the coordinator for the project, and Brigitte Braun, responsible for communications. The section features a collection of recent press

releases covering key developments and project milestones, such as efforts to improve food sustainability in Ireland and Portugal, updates from local living labs, and broader reflections on food system resilience in the face of climate change.

The Press Corner also includes downloadable communication materials, such as FEAST logo files in multiple formats, a style guide, and a curated set of high-quality project photographs, making it easy for journalists and stakeholders to access official branding.

Figure 14 Screenshot of the FEAST website press corner page (Accessed on 18.06.2025)

In addition to the project website press corner, the press releases have also been published in the Media Bulletin of the openscience.eu platform ([Media Bulletin for Research Projects | openscience.eu](#)).

2.3.3.3 Project Brochures and other Materials

A suite of materials that are essential for uni- and- bidirectional communication activities for use at scientific conferences, fairs, and other events have been developed. Table 17 provides an overview of the communication activities and their state of implementation.

Table 17 Description and state of implementation of FEAST for uni- and- bidirectional communication

Type	Short description and state of implementation
Brochures	FEAST Yearly Highlights is a brochure of project achievements, published once a year in October.

	<p>FEAST 1st year package and 2nd year package is available in English and can be downloaded from the website.</p> <p>To increase FEAST visibility, the brochure has been translated into Dutch, German, Portuguese, French, Italian, Polish, Danish, and North Macedonian. FEAST partners check the translations for accuracy before they are made available for download.</p> <p>Next steps: Make the documents available in the download section</p> <p>State - Ongoing</p>
<p>Posters</p>	<p>Conference posters were presented at the NetworkNature annual meeting 2023 conference in Brussels, at the CLEVER Cities conference in Hamburg (2023), FOSSNET network event in Oxford (2025).</p> <p>Next steps: Collect and upload more posters presented by FEAST partners.</p> <p>State - Ongoing</p>
<p>Promotional video</p>	<p>In total 57 videos were produced and published on FEAST's YouTube channel and a selection is also embedded on the website.</p> <p>Next step:</p> <p>State - Ongoing</p>
<p>Project templates</p>	<p>State - finished</p>

Figure 15 shows two example rollups developed for the FEAST KickOff event in Heidelberg on Oct 5-6, 2022. The left one displays the main FEAST themes (food, health and sustainability) in a simple way through the three icons specially designed for this purpose. The rollup on the right side shows the key facts of FEAST e.g. number of involved countries, partners, and living lab sites.

Figure 15 Rollups developed for the FEAST KickOff

2.3.3.4 Social Media

Social media allows us to reach a wide, targeted audience, maximizing FEAST's impact and successfully exploiting our project results. Social media is being used for both our communication and dissemination. Before launching our project on a specific social media platform, the pros and cons of each specific platform are evaluated.

As social media platforms evolve over time, projects like FEAST are always in the situation to evaluate their strategies. Questions like:

- Does the platform share the values of the project?
- Is the audience we want to reach changing?
- Is the business model of the platform changing, and might this impact the project?
- Are we also reaching our collaborators via the platform, i.e. other projects?

One good example of how a platform is changing is X (Twitter). Since Elon Musk bought Twitter, not only has the name changed to X, but also their users and how people communicate on the platform have changed. At the same time, X remains one of the most used platforms for engaging with other Horizon Europe/2020 projects. While other projects do not belong to our primary target audience group, they are relevant for the exchange of information and amplification of our posts.

Due to these developments, the FEAST DEC working group decided to take on a passive role on X (Twitter) in mid-2023. The account will continue to exist, but we will reduce our activities and observe how X continues to develop.

Another example is ResearchGate (*Home Feed | ResearchGate*); in February 2023 a FEAST project site was created on ResearchGate. On March 31, 2023, ResearchGate retired the projects feature and removed all projects from the site. See the following announcement: *ResearchGate Updates | Projects have been discontinued. Here's what we learned — and what we're working on next*

Other relevant channels that need to be further analysed for use in FEAST include (not implemented yet):

Meta – Four of the largest social media platforms belong to Meta. All of them have more than one billion active users per month: Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger.

- Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/>)
 - State: Not-started yet
- Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/>)
 - State: Started
- Mastodon (<https://mastodon.social/>)
 - State: Not-started. Not identified as an important social media platform for the project, as it currently has approx. 2 million users and is not known in all EU countries.

Over 59% of the EU population uses social media to ensure our messages are getting to the right audiences, we use a carefully curated list of social media hashtags that reach a wide audience and those that are more niche to ensure our messages are effectively reaching our target audiences. Some examples of hashtags we are currently using include:

#FEAST2030, #food, #foodwaste, #foodsecurity, #foodavailability, #foodaffordability, #foodsystems, #foodpolicy, #health, #healthydiet, #hunger, #malnutrition, #sustainability, #foodjustice

This list will be continually updated over the course of the project.

2.3.3.4.1 FEAST's Social Media Channels

Table 18 shows the already implemented social media channels, including the target groups and the hyperlink to the relevant channel.

Table 18 FEAST implemented social media channels, date 25.11.2023

Channel	Target groups	Hyperlink
<p>LinkedIn</p> <p>Status: active</p>	<p>Research and education, businesses policy makers, civil society organizations, municipalities and local authorities, associations representing different stakeholders in the food system.</p>	<p>LinkedIn FEAST2030</p>
<p>X (Twitter)</p> <p>Status: inactive since May 2023</p>	<p>Research and education, businesses policy makers, civil society organizations, municipalities and local authorities, associations representing different stakeholders in the food system, citizens, local media (including newspapers), press companies, communities.</p>	<p>X (Twitter) FEAST2030</p>
<p>YouTube</p> <p>Status: active</p>	<p>Research and education, businesses policy makers, civil society organizations, municipalities and local authorities, associations representing different stakeholders in the food system, education and school communities (teachers, students, parents, etc.), citizens, small farmers.</p>	<p>YouTube FEAST2030</p>

We started FEAST's LinkedIn channel in July 2022 with posts being made at least once per week. Regular posting ensures that interested users are always informed about the latest progress of the project. A total of 1,048 people are already following FEAST's activities and the posts have generated more than 37,000 views per year. Table 19 and Table 20 show the type of industry and professional functions of the followers. The two industry types that have the greatest representation among FEAST followers are 'Research Services' and 'Higher Education'.

Table 19 Ranking of LinkedIn followers and industry type of followers (18.06.2025) and rank change.

Rank	Industry	Total followers
1 (+1)	Higher Education	173 (16.4%)
2 (-1)	Research Services	154 (14.6%)
3 (+1)	Non-profit Organizations	69 (6,5%)
4 (-1)	Government Administration	60 (5,7%)
5 (+2)	Civic and Social Organizations	42 (4%)
6 (-1)	Public Policy Offices	32 (3%)
7 (+1)	Business Consulting and Services	32 (3%)
8 (-2)	Hospitals and Health Care	29 (2.7%)
9 (new)	Food and Beverage Services	19 (1.8%)
10 (-)	Biotechnology Research	15 (1.4%)

Table 20 Ranking of LinkedIn followers and job function (18.06.2025), and rank change.

Rank	Job function	Total followers
1 (-)	Research	163 (15.4%)
2 (-)	Education	120 (11.3%)
3 (-)	Business Development	99 (9.4%)
4 (+4)	Community and Social Services	66 (6.2%)
5 (-1)	Program and Project Management	59 (5.6%)
6 (-1)	Operations	55 (5.2%)
7 (-1)	Media and Communication	54 (5.1%)
8 (-1)	Healthcare Services	53 (5%)
9 (-)	Information Technology	25 (2.4%)
10 (new)	Consulting	22 (2.1%)

FEAST's YouTube channel includes 57 videos and has 5,023 views and 27,700 impressions. Impressions include how many times the video thumbnails were shown to viewers on YouTube, not on external sites or apps. Figure 16 shows the views of FEAST's YouTube videos by traffic source from between October 2022 and November 2023 and Figure 17 the the views between December 2023 and May 2025. Most of the views come from external sources, external sources are websites and apps in which FEAST videos are embedded. Figure 18 shows the breakdown of the external sources

between October 2022 and November 2023. LinkedIn is in first place, followed by Instagram, LinkedIn App, google search and the FEAST website. Figure 19 provides an overview of the external sources December 2023 and May 2025. This illustrates how important it is to link content across platforms. A full list of all FEAST's YouTube videos can be found in Table A3 1 in Annex 3.

Traffic source	Views ↓	Watch time (hours)	Average view duration	Impressions
<input type="checkbox"/> Total	1,607	19.0	0:42	13,158
<input type="checkbox"/> External	625 38.9%	8.4 44.1%	0:48	–
<input type="checkbox"/> Channel pages	378 23.5%	3.5 18.3%	0:33	2,471
<input type="checkbox"/> Direct or unknown	182 11.3%	1.9 9.9%	0:37	–
<input type="checkbox"/> YouTube search	142 8.8%	1.3 6.9%	0:33	2,698
<input type="checkbox"/> Playlists	129 8.0%	1.8 9.6%	0:50	935

Figure 16 Views, watch time, average view duration and impressions of FEAST's YouTube videos by traffic source, between October 2022 and November 2023

Traffic source	Views ↓	Watch time (hours)	Average view duration	Impressions
<input type="checkbox"/> Total	3,596	92.5	1:32	40,091
<input type="checkbox"/> External	1,247 34.7%	29.6 32.0%	1:25	–
<input type="checkbox"/> Channel pages	856 23.8%	15.2 16.4%	1:03	10,706
<input type="checkbox"/> Playlists	331 9.2%	15.3 16.5%	2:46	3,514
<input type="checkbox"/> YouTube search	293 8.2%	4.3 4.6%	0:52	8,659
<input type="checkbox"/> Direct or unknown	285 7.9%	7.7 8.3%	1:37	–

Figure 17 Views, watch time, average view duration and impressions of FEAST's YouTube videos by traffic source, between December 2023 and May 2025

Traffic source > External	Views ↓	Watch time (hours)	Average view duration
<input type="checkbox"/> Total	625	8.4	0:48
<input type="checkbox"/> linkedin.com	158 25.3%	2.4 28.4%	0:54
<input type="checkbox"/> instagram.com	63 10.1%	0.2 1.9%	0:09
<input type="checkbox"/> linkedin.android	45 7.2%	0.6 6.6%	0:44
<input type="checkbox"/> Google Search	41 6.6%	0.4 4.6%	0:33
<input type="checkbox"/> feast2030.eu	21 3.4%	0.3 3.8%	0:53

Figure 18 Views of FEAST's YouTube videos by traffic source External, between October 2022 and November 2023

Traffic source > External	Views ↓ ▲	Watch time (hours)	Average view duration
<input type="checkbox"/> Total	1,247	29.6	1:25
<input type="checkbox"/> Google Search	114 9.1%	3.0 10.0%	1:33
<input type="checkbox"/> feast2030.eu	91 7.3%	1.6 5.6%	1:05
<input type="checkbox"/> whatsapp.com	72 5.8%	1.7 5.7%	1:24
<input type="checkbox"/> linkedin.com	71 5.7%	1.9 6.6%	1:38
<input type="checkbox"/> YouTube	46 3.7%	1.3 4.3%	1:38

Figure 19 Views of FEAST's YouTube videos by traffic source External, between December 2023 and May 2025

2.3.3.4.2 FEAST Partner Social Media Channels

In addition to the project's main social media channels, social media channels managed by the FEAST WP lead organisations (Table 21; the full list can be found in the Annex) are being used to maximize outreach and leverage network effects.

Table 21 Social media channels managed by the FEAST WP lead organisations

Partner	Hyperlink
University of Heidelberg (Lead: WP1, 5, and 9)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/university-of-heidelberg X (Twitter): https://twitter.com/UniHeidelberg Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/uniheidelberg/?hl=en Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/uniheidelberg
EuroHealthNet (Lead: WP7)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurohealthnet/mycompany/ X (Twitter): https://twitter.com/EuroHealthNet Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/EuroHealthNet.eu/
Sciensano (Lead: WP3)	X (Twitter): https://twitter.com/sciensano https://www.sciensano.be/en
ICLEI Europe (Lead: WP4)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/iclei-europe X (Twitter): @ICLEI_Europe @SF4C_Project @buy_betterfood
Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture (Lead: WP6)	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Inrae.France/ X (Twitter): https://twitter.com/INRAE_France Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/INRAE/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/test-science/
open science for open societies (Lead: WP8)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/os4os X (Twitter): https://twitter.com/os4os_

	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/_os4os/
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (Lead: WP2)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/scuola-superiore-sant'anna/ X (Twitter): https://twitter.com/ScuolaSantanna/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/scuolasuperioresantanna

2.3.3.5 Partner Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Resources

In addition to partner websites and social media channels, FEAST partners are involved in other networks or operate platforms themselves that serve as resources for FEAST DEC activities. Table 22 shows the WP leads specific DEC resources.

Table 22 FEAST specific sites and channels

Partner	Hyperlink and Purpose
University of Heidelberg (Lead: WP1, 5 and 9)	UKHD – under development FabLab - http://www.opendotlab.it/fablab/ Growth hacking – myLabel - https://mylabel.io
EuroHealthNet (Lead: WP7)	EU Food Policy Coalition: https://foodpolicycoalition.eu/ CHAIN: https://www.ntnu.edu/chain EuroHealthNet Magazine : https://eurohealthnet-magazine.eu/ EuroHealthNet Communication Network
ICLEI Europe (Lead: WP4)	Buy Better Food campaign - https://buybetterfood.eu/ City Food program - https://cityfood-program.org/ ICLEI iNews (newsletter) and online newsroom (https://iclei-europe.org/news/) CitiesWithNature - https://citieswithnature.org/ NetworkNature - https://networknature.eu/ SchoolFood4Change - https://schoolfood4change.eu/ ICLEI Sustainable Procurement Platform - https://sustainable-procurement.org/
open science for open societies (Lead: WP8)	www.openscience.eu - The Platform can be used for the dissemination and exploitation of our results. Mainly to promote FEAST's OS results.

2.3.4 Events

2.3.4.1 Project internal events

The events that will take place annually include:

- Annual online General Assembly meetings (every spring).
- In person General Assembly meetings (second year in autumn)

2.3.4.2 External meetings/Events

Table 23 shows a selection of events and meetings FEAST partners attended where they presented FEAST-related material.

Table 23 Selection of events and meetings in which FEAST partners have participated.

No	Partner and date	Type of event and description of event
1	EuroHealthNet 23.09.2022	Collaboration with EU-funded projects – Presentation of FEAST on Health Inequalities in food systems at the joint meeting of the Scientific and Stakeholder Advisory Boards of the JPI “A healthy diet for a healthy life” (JPI HDHL). EuroHealthNet presented FEAST at this advisory board meeting, speaking on health inequalities and explaining how FEAST is going to address this issue. After the presentation, a debate followed with questions from CSOs, member state representatives, patient representative organisations and medical doctors.
2	EuroHealthNet 26.09.2022	Conference – EuroHealthNet presented FEAST at the European Health Forum in Gastein. 26-29 SEPTEMBER 2022 the 25th European Health Forum Gastein. EuroHealthNet’s Policy Manager spoke about FEAST in a panel on Co-creating better food systems in Europe: The role of consumers' informed choices in transitioning to healthier and more sustainable food systems.
3	EuroHealthNet 28.11.2022	Conference – FEAST presentation at a FEPS (Foundation for European Progressive Studies) Expert Meeting "Breaking Down the Silos: Climate Mainstreaming and Holistic Policy Design". EuroHealthNet participated in this roundtable to discuss health challenges in food systems. During the discussions, EuroHealthNet presented the work done and planned in FEAST as an example of how a systemic approach to food systems to benefit health.
4	myLabel 29.11.2022	Conference – Testify myLabel-FEAST in the context of the “Ambition Europe day”. MyLabel was invited to testify in context of the “Ambition Europe day” organized by the Auvergne Rhône-Alpes Region on November 29. The CEO of myLabel spoke at an important time of the day, in the plenary room of the region's headquarters, a great opportunity to talk about and discover the FEAST project.

5	Good Food Oxfordshire 01.05.2023	<p>Round table event – Childhood Food Poverty Policy recommendations. A roundtable event on Childhood Nutrition was held at the University of Oxford in May 2023. In total 65 stakeholders came together to share local experiences and explore opportunities for collective action. The views from this event have helped to not only shape the policy recommendations but also were used to inform areas of interest for the Oxfordshire LL.</p>
6	IPVC and Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alto Minho 08.05.2023	<p>Meeting – Strategy alignment meeting and formalization of partnerships between FEAST CIM/IPVC team and associations for regional development AdriMinho and Adril, May 8, Viana do Castelo, Portugal.</p>
7	University of Lodzki 30.05.2023	<p>Conference – Active participation in Social Policy Congress in Warsaw, Poland (40th National Conference of Social Politicians; "Social Policy as a Foundation of Social and Economic Development") organised under the auspices of the Social Insurance Institution and the Polish Academy of Sciences. Speech on "Local food policy and sustainable consumption as new, interdisciplinary challenges for social policy". Information about the FEAST project included in speech, both verbally and visually.</p>
8	ICLEI Europe 07.06.2023	<p>Conference – NetworkNature Annual Event. Poster presentation.</p>
9	Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alto Minho and IPVC 13.06.2023	<p>Meeting – Alto Minho's baseline diagnosis preliminary results presentation. Aiming to have a clearer picture of the approach undertaken in Alto Minho's schools on food-related topics, CIM Alto Minho and IPVC carried out a baseline diagnosis targeting both Alto Minho municipalities and Alto Minho's school groupings. The preliminary results of the diagnosis were presented during the Alto Minho Education Committee meeting, held on June 13th, 2023.</p>
10	Commune d'Avignon 15.06.2023	<p>Education and training events – Event on food for children. It was a free event open to the municipal schools to experiment many aspects of what sustainable food could mean. Various activities were proposed to the children: discovering bees' world, reflecting on food marketing, planting seeds, participating in a cooking workshop, etc..</p>
11	University of Lodzki 19.06.2023	<p>Conference – Participation in 6th International Conference on Aging & Technology Fair organised by the Czech Active Aging Centre, Keynote Company, International Visegrad Fund under the auspices of Czech Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs. Plenary conference speech "Food Insecurity among the Elderly: Case Study of the Polish "Living Lab" within the FEAST Project". Presentation of FEAST's main goals & assumptions. Public screening of Lodz Living Lab video.</p>

12	IPVC, os4os and ICLEI Europe 26.09.2023	Conference – Poster at Clever Cities Nature in the City conference. Poster of LL Alto Minho's activities.
13	Guldborg Municipality, City of Gent, IPVC, ICLEI Europe and os4os 27.09.2023	Conference – Session at Clever Cities conference "Nature in the City" - Co-Developing Community Based Solutions for Healthy and Sustainable City Food Systems. This world cafe style workshop featured Living Labs from the Horizon Europe Food Systems project FEAST. Emphasis was placed on links between sustainable and healthy city food systems for all, nature-based solutions, and co-creative planning processes. Through the presentation of real-life challenges the Living Labs face on their journey, the goal was to foster cross-pollination and enhance collaboration throughout the disciplines of food systems and nature based solutions. After a brief introduction of three representative Living Labs (Guldborgsund, Denmark/Gent, Belgium/Alto Minho, Portugal) we will gathered in small groups to discuss the challenges these Living Labs encounter in starting co-creation processes. The involved stakeholders vary from non-governmental, public organizations to educational institutions. We wanted to showcase how co-creation can work in real life and what awaits along the way.
14	Good Food Oxfordshire 01.10.2023	Conference – Consumer Data Research Centre (CDRC) annual conference. Presentation made by GFO Director at the CDRC annual forum.
15	Azienda USL Toscana 16.10.2023	Meeting – Pre-kick-off event: presentation of Tuscany Living Lab to all Health Promotion Units of Tuscany Region. Showcasing of the FEAST project and TNO Living Lab: context, trigger for participation, objectives, status of activities, outcomes and future steps. Attendees showed great interest in the project and expressed willingness to be updated on subsequent activities.
16	University of Lodzki 20.10.2023	Meeting – FEAST project got an official nomination as a "Research Project of the Future" from the Polish Smart Development Forum. The FEAST project has been selected by the jury of the Polish Smart Development Forum as a nominee for the award of a Research Project of the Future. Dr Kaja Zapadowska-Kling, one of the FEAST team members at the University of Lodz, got an award of a Scientist of the Future in a category "A Woman of Science who changes the world". She introduced the idea of FEAST project during the final gala.
17	SUSMETRO 26.10.2023	Conference – FoodSHIFT 2030 Policy Conference. Keynote and panel debate with input on FEAST.
18	Good Food Oxfordshire 08.11.2023	Clustering activities – Annual Celebration. This event is an opportunity for the GFO team and the wider network to come together and celebrate our collective successes from the past year. As part of the event Fiona Steel, GFO Manager, presented the key

		<p>projects and campaigns, of which FEAST was one. After the presentation there was an opportunity to network, and for the project team to promote the projects vision and planned outcomes with key stakeholders.</p>
19	<p>University of Heidelberg, EuroHealthNet and EAT Foundation 08-11.11.2023</p>	<p>Conference – Plenary session at the annual European Public Health Association (EUPHA2023) conference. In the plenary, organised by Caroline Costongs (EuroHealthNet - FEAST partner) and Suzanne Costello, the panelists highlighted concrete actions to address our imbalanced food systems. Key takeaways: Prof Tim Lang: get citizens involved in demanding change for our food systems Dr Francesco Branca: drive ambitious policies to create a new baseline for what is possible Dr Gunhild Anker Stordalen (EAT - FEAST partner): bridging silos across policy, science and business to transform food systems</p>
20	<p>University College Cork 10.11.2023</p>	<p>Conference – CFPC EUPHA2023 Presentation Workshop. INFORMAS and FEAST partnered in a session at the EPH (Europeach Public Heath Conference) in Dublin this year. As part of the session the video showed Janas Harrington from UCC Cork, a FEAST partner who shared the work of the Cork Food Policy Council. CFPC not only works on ongoing policy interventions at city level, but also organises educational and community-building events to bring local producers, cooks and eaters together.</p>
21	<p>ICLEI Europe and City of Gent 16.11.2023</p>	<p>Education and training event – Kantine Zukunft Talk Food Environments.</p>
22	<p>IPVC 24.11.2023</p>	<p>Education and training event – Heroes crew joining FEAST (6-9 year old children), fruit paintball - colouring activities (6-8 year old children) and work on recognising local products and assets in the form of a quiz . Guess who I am? (9-12 year old children). Work to recognise products and assets from the region and raise awareness of healthier eating habits.</p>
23	<p>UKHD, EuroHealthNet, RUC 05.03.2024</p>	<p>Clustering activities – Food2030 clustering event in Brussels hosted by the CLEVERFOOD project. UKHD, EuroHealthNet and RUC coordinated a clustering session on the theme of “Policy and governance for food system transformation”.</p>
24	<p>UKHD, RUC 20.03.2024</p>	<p>Conference – UKHD and RUC presented at the START conference in Copenhagen, hosted by the Copenhagen business school, on using Living Labs as a method for catalysing food system transformation. UKHD showcased the living lab approach and methodology used in the FEAST project.</p>

25	UKHD 05.06.2024	Conference – UKHD presenting at the health.tech conference on the role of food systems as a critical determinant of health in promoting health and preventing disease.
26	Sciensano, EuroHealthNet, UKHD 05.09.2024	Clustering activities – Sciensano, EuroHealthNet and UKHD presenting about FEAST activities at a clustering event held by the Informas network in Brussels.
27	EuroHealthNet, UKHD 27.09.2024	Conference – EuroHealthNet and UKHD organized a panel session on the barriers and facilitators for progressive policies that could support the transition to healthier, more sustainable and more just food systems.
28	Azienda USL Toscana 27.9.2024	Education event – Bright Night 27/9/24 hosted by Sant'Anna, targeting citizens in Tuscany region to create visibility for TNO LL and foster healthy eating.
29	Università degli Studi di Scienze Gastronomiche 28.9.2024	Congress – Presentation at the Congress “Shaping Gastronomy: Regenerating Food Systems and Societies”
30	os4os, UKHD 5.12.2024	Clustering activities – os4os and UKHD presenting at a webinar organized by DRG4FOOD & FOODITY on outcomes-based data standardization for promoting healthier, more sustainable and more just food systems.
31	UKHD 6.12.2024	Clustering activities – UKHD presenting in a parallel working session at the final event of the Life Climate Smart Chefs event on the synergies in approaches between that project and FEAST.
32	UKHD 22.01.2025	Clustering activities – UKHD presenting at a clustering webinar organized Policy Officer Unit B.2 – Bioeconomy & Food Systems of the European Commission.
33	UKHD 06.02.2025	Education event – UKHD presenting on FEAST work at an event organized at the King’s Fund in London exploring policy options to address food insecurity for children.
34	UKHD 20.03.2025	Clustering activities – UKHD presented at a panel session at an event in Brussels organized by MAIA and I-CHANGE on the role of citizens in sustainable transitions in Europe
35	UKHD, RUC 26.03.2025	Clustering activities – UKHD and RUC presenting at the FoSSNet conference in Oxford on the approach that FEAST took to develop its living lab network. A poster was also presented.
36	UKHD 29.04-30.04.2025	Clustering activities – UKHD collaborating with the CLEVERFOOD project to present a joint session at the START conference in Copenhagen, on the facilitators and barriers to transitioning towards plant-based food systems.

37	GFO, UKHD 19.05.2025	Education event – GFO and UKHD presenting at an event organized by Green Templeton College at the University of Oxford to outline the approach used in FEAST to support living labs to adopt rigorous scientific methods to generate evidence on the impact of their interventions.
38	UKHD 20.06.2025	Conference – UKHD presenting on the approach FEAST takes to multilevel governance at the British Ecological Society symposium on Nature, Farming and Food held at the University of Oxford.

3 Inclusive, intersectional and non-stigmatising communications

3.1 Inclusive and intersectional communications and representation

FEAST is actively inviting and working with individuals representing the full spectra, diversity and intersectionality of European society (e.g. characteristics including gender, race, ability, socio-economic status, culture, language, technology access, etc.) through FEAST team members and associated stakeholders. We are actively integrating and applying intersectional analyses across all components of the project to ensure that we are continuously evaluating norms and stereotypes, particularly linked to vulnerable groups, while also ensuring that we are considering and addressing the emerging needs of the full diversity of European society. This is being achieved by utilising inclusive and neutral language and avoiding narratives surrounding different roles and social constellations that reinforce potential stereotypes. All outputs are reviewed by multiple partners, who themselves have varied identities, to ensure that any given author's positionality does not result in problematically oriented content. Opportunities for professional development on this front, such as trainings and educational material, are also being sought out and shared with partners, to ensure that our inclusive and intersectional lens extends to consortium members' internal and external communication and not only project outputs.

Furthermore, a small working group within WP8 is advising on the inclusivity and intersectionality of our communications, including our partners from the University of Lodz, who are part of the Women's Studies centre which has extensive experience in the gender dimension. For the most critical communications linked to WP-related tasks we also consult with our Independent Ethics Advisor, Abha Saxena, to ensure that our work adheres to ethical principles.

Given that FEAST addresses all elements of the food system, the general approach we are taking is to (see Figure 20):

- (1) Ensure that we are collecting and analysing information from different sectors of the food system (i.e., consumers, producers, distributors, retailers) in a way that accounts for the diversity of European society by actively recruiting individuals across different groups, particularly vulnerable groups, for their views while also accounting for these dimensions in our analyses (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7).
- (2) Ensure that FEAST's co-designed community-based, technology-based and policy-based solutions are done with diverse individuals, and in a way that takes account of their needs and preferences, so these solutions can be actively used by all EU citizens across all groups to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour (WP4, WP5, WP7).
- (3) Ensure that FEAST's dissemination, exploitation and communication fully accounts for the different dimensions, as outlined above, while also being designed to reach them in ways they want, and are likely, to be reached (WP7, WP8).

Figure 20 FEAST approach to address the gender dimension throughout the project

3.2 Non-stigmatising terms about health

Food and health are intertwined; it is difficult to advocate for a shift in the food system without addressing and celebrating the potential for improved health outcomes at the population level. At the same time, it is essential to avoid language that stigmatises certain dietary practices or diet-related conditions and illnesses. FEAST achieves this by following the guidance outlined in the *Rural Health Toolkit*, which encourages centering individuals and communities in communication, rather than a condition or circumstance. For example, we would use the phrase 'individuals impacted by malnutrition', rather than 'malnourished individuals'.

3.3 Accessibility of information

FEAST's main language of communication is English, but given that activities are being carried out at a local level in different countries, more targeted material is also being developed for specific channels, tasks, and outputs that are aligned with preferred communication channels for local actors. We are monitoring the need for the translation of materials, and local teams are organising the work of translation into country-specific languages in different communication modalities, such as text and audio. Furthermore, English language communication written for the general public are written at the 8th grade level to ensure the content is accessible to the widest possible audience.

3.4 Gender Impact Assessment Training and Tools

A series of three internal webinars, which were carried out between October 2024 and January 2025, aimed at enhancing gender-balanced and intersectional research and communication across the FEAST consortium. These sessions, organized in collaboration with the University of Lodz and the communication team, provided targeted training and practical tools to support inclusive language and representation in both internal and external outputs. The webinars emphasized the importance of recognizing and addressing gender dynamics, cultural context, and intersecting identities in scientific research and communication. Participants explored case studies, engaged in reflective exercises, and received guidance on how to embed inclusive practices into their everyday workflows, ranging from report writing and visual media to stakeholder engagement. Although designed with the communication team in mind, these trainings were open to all research and innovation teams within FEAST to ensure a shared institutional commitment to equity in communication. The initiative reflects an integrated approach to fostering awareness and capacity-building, aligning with broader diversity and inclusion organizational values. As a result, the team is now better equipped to critically assess and improve the gender sensitivity and inclusivity of their communications, thereby contributing to more representative and impactful science dissemination. The recordings of the webinar, as well as the presentations and links to tools, are available in the FEAST internal Teams channel to support new joining team members as well.

4 Academic Dissemination

Knowledge is being shared at all stages of FEAST's research and innovation lifecycle and across different disciplines. The FEAST consortium is committed to the implementation of open practices (open access, open source, open data, etc.). Members who are already actively adhering to and applying these principles are supporting consortium members new to the approach in integrating

open practices into their academic dissemination work. FEAST's use of open practices underlines the consortium's commitment to FEAST's MAA approach and empowering food system actors with knowledge to drive change on the ground, by reducing barriers to access. The Open Science (OS) strategy is coordinated by os4os (Open Science for Open Societies), which has extensive experience in designing, implementing and promoting open science practices.

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles are the basis for FEAST's research work. As FAIR does not systematically mean "Open", we are also following the principle 'as open as possible and as closed as necessary' for output sharing and achieving a high impact. Several measures are being implemented to foster OS of the research outputs (scientific publications, data, software, algorithms, protocols) as highlighted in Table 24.

Table 24 FEAST OS roadmap framework: Research output and FEAST measures to address the FAIR principles and ensure reproducibility

OS Integration across FEAST	FEAST measures to address the FAIR principles and ensure early sharing & reproducibility of results
OS Approaches & Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>OS capacity building</u>: All partners are being trained on the latest OS practices and tools (i.e., latest standards and services created/validated by EOSC). - <u>Citizen science</u>: Research design based on citizen sciences methods - i.e., multistakeholder co-creation processes and integration of non-scientists into research live cycle.
OS Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>General information (FEAST website)</u>: A section dedicated to OS is being integrated into the FEAST website (with links to research outputs, training materials) and a public download section (data hub) for information which cannot be stored on EC data spaces is being provided. - <u>Licensing & copyright</u>: FEAST is using systematically, and obligatory, open licensing models (mainly CC-BY), as defined by the <i>Open Knowledge Foundation</i>. The licensing models are applied to publications, content, data and code. - <u>Research outputs</u>: Research outputs (i.e., figures, models, workflows, software) and data are being made open and machine-understandable (i.e., sharing of metadata and description of how artefacts and data can be used for assessment and reproduction of research results). FEAST research data align with the EC strategy on <i>Web of FAIR Data</i> and Services to interlink data spaces. Software will be identified by the use of persistent identifier (PID), code will be stored at partner Git repositories (i.e., <i>GitHub</i> or <i>GitLab</i>), and the FEAST Git repository (which will be launched early in the project). - <u>Storage</u>: Certified trusted repositories applying FAIR principles are being used. FEAST cloud services (i.e., model exploitation, data analysis, exploitation tool kit) will be made publicly available over the <i>EOSC marketplace</i>. - <u>Scientific publications</u>: Scientific publications are being shared over preprint platforms wherever possible (i.e., as long as the target journal allow preprint publishing). Furthermore, research plan(s) are being made available

in *Zenodo* or other platforms allowing preregistration and preprints. At least ten publications will be submitted in *Open Research Europe* (ORE). Further, articles will be published in open access (OA) journals linked with *ORCID iD*. Outputs and findings from our work will also contribute to openly accessible *Lancet publications* (Lancet Health and Climate Change countdown, EAT Lancet 2.0).

5 FEAST's Community of Practice: External Collaboration with the EU Food Systems Community

FEAST is building and growing a Community of Practice (CoP), which functions as a platform to bring together relevant European Stakeholders (mainly virtually) for targeted exchange on topics that fall within the CoP scope.

During Q2 2023, the CoP concept draft was finalized (V9.0), outlining the CoP scope, objectives, added value, structure and key activities. For example, the CoP scope has now been defined as shown below in Figure 21.

Figure 21 Community of Practice Scope Areas

With these scope areas in mind, the preliminary CoP objectives are:

- To facilitate knowledge brokerage
- To generate policy impact
- To stimulate industry dialogue

Regarding the target group of the CoP, Living Labs will be the main target of CoP activities and objectives. Living Labs have been chosen as the CoP target group in order to support practical, on-the-ground challenges regarding food and health, by stimulating the exchange of effective solutions and enabling the engagement of experts from academic and policy fields where needed. In this context, the CoP will facilitate the translation of research and policy into concrete actions among Living Labs, whilst building and sharing knowledge across Living Labs.

Launch of the CoP

On Monday 25th September 2023, the CoP was officially launched among the FEAST Living Labs in collaboration with WP4. The CoP concept was presented and Living Labs were encouraged to register. Since the launch among FEAST Living Labs, the CoP has also been launched in the FOODSHIFT2030 and PLAN'EAT projects, inviting their Living Labs to join the CoP. The invitation flyer for Living Labs is shown in Figure 22 (left). At the time of writing (November 2023), 21 registrations for the CoP have been received from Living Lab representatives. These registrations represent 14 unique city regions. The scope areas of (1) Behaviour Change and (3) Food Environments appear as the two most popular / priority scope areas among registered Living Labs. In May 2025 the CoP registrations had grown to more than 50 registrations.

CoP Events

Several CoP events have been scheduled for Q1 2024. These events will take the form of 1.5 hour sessions dedicated to a case submitted by CoP members. This case will take the form of a challenge or goal from a Living Lab for which they require extra support. The sessions will be facilitated by the CoP organizing core who will develop a session program based on the case requirements. Figure 22 (right) shows the Call for Cases flyer distributed to CoP members in preparation of the CoP sessions.

Figure 22 Community of Practice Invitation Flyer for Living Labs (left) and Call for Cases Flyer (right)

Each session is summarized in a CoP compact document to highlight the discussion and the focus and made available on the website.

After the first CoP year, there was an internal strategy meeting to evaluate the strategy and improve the impact of these online events.

Collaborations with other networks

The CoP is structured into three main groups (Table 25):

Table 25 Structure of FEAST's Community of Practice (CoP)

	Description	Who	Engagement Level
1. Organizing Core	Task 8.4 partners who contribute to the set-up, design, and organization of the CoP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUS (lead) • UKH • ScS • EHNet • EAT • FIBL • ICLEI • USG • UGR 	Collaborate
2. CoP Members	Representatives who form the bulk of the CoP and participate in regular CoP activities. These representatives are the main target group for the CoP objectives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FEAST Consortium • EU Food Project Family Consortium Members • Other relevant Horizon & EU projects 	Involve, Collaborate & Empower
3. Network Partners	Network partners are welcome to join as regular CoP members, but will most likely be involved on a more ad-hoc basis when there are targeted activities and discussions relevant to their interests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare professionals • City officials • Relevant NGOs / CSOs • Industry players • Educational institutes • FabLab Network • MUFPP cities 	Consult

A key strength of the FEAST consortium are the strong networks of its partners. These networks provide the project with accessible channels for our DEC activities and to empower and support Europe's stakeholders in all parts of the food systems (Figure 23):

Figure 23 FEAST key scaling routes to scale impact during and after the project end date

During the first year of the project, the CoP has identified other food systems networks and social media campaigns to which FEAST can participate. This work will occur alongside clustering activities with sibling Horizon projects involved in food systems, many of which FEAST partners are already actively contributing to:

- **FOODTRAILS** (H2020 - Roskilde University and EAT): Food Trails are piloting 11 activities in participating cities in order to better co-create urban food policy. The goal is to make the farm-to-fork journey sustainable and to empower communities, promote zero-waste use of resources, promote environmentally friendly behaviour change and ensure people have healthy and secure diets.
- **SchoolFood4Change** (H2020 – ICLEI, Ghent): Starting in January 2022, 34 partners from 12 European countries (including 16 local governments) will work over four years to implement solutions aimed at switching to healthy and sustainable school meals with a whole school food approach. Over 3,000 schools with more than 600,000 children and young people in 12 EU Member States will be impacted.
- **BUY BETTER FOOD** (Coalition of members including ICLEI): Campaign calling for the uptake of public food procurement rules that work for the environment, consumers, and workers, and that provide healthy food to European citizens in public places such as schools, hospitals and elderly care homes.
- **JPI-PEN** (University College Cork): JPI-PEN will provide an overview of public policies with direct/indirect potential influence on food and physical activity policy environments. It will build on existing tools including the Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI) developed by the INFORMAS group.
- **INFORMAS** Group (Sciensano): INFORMAS (International Network for Food and Obesity / Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) Research, Monitoring and Action Support) is a global network of public-interest organisations and researchers that aim to monitor, benchmark and support public and private sector actions to increase healthy food environments and reduce obesity, NCDs and their related inequalities. They have developed a variety of tools to evaluate food environments and businesses including Food EPI, BIA-Obesity and BIA-Sustainability. 43 countries are actively using INFORMAS' food environment and policy surveys.
- **EcoFoodMap** (Leuven2030): EcoFoodMap is an interactive tool that maps the food system in and around Leuven. The tool provides the necessary information about all initiatives, actors, experts and indicators in the Leuven food system. The goal is to stimulate new collaborations and provide insights that further improve connections and decision-making for a more sustainable and resilient urban food system.

- **Lancet Commissions** (EAT Foundation, University of Heidelberg, Sciensano): EAT Lancet 1.0 and the newly launched EAT Lancet 2.0; Lancet Health and Climate Change Countdown; Global Syndemic Commission.

In the period between M18-M35, FEAST connected with the following projects:

TealHelix is an EU Horizon Europe project that aims to empower consumers with personalised and inclusive labelling approaches to food sustainability. By using motivational matching, the project develops labelling strategies and digital innovations to address consumer resistance and promote informed decision-making. In the project, traditional, digital, and smart labelling in retail and online settings in six pilot countries (Germany, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Greece, and Poland) is going to be tested while establishing integrity guidelines and industry standards. It aims to promote sustainable food choices and engage diverse consumers effectively by leveraging interdisciplinary expertise, big data, and AI tools.

FEAST attended the general assembly of TealHelix in 2025 in Copenhagen

Vision4FOOD is an EU Horizon Europe project that aims to build sustainable and resilient food systems by creating governance models that help local actors make better decisions. It works in five regions, with diverse challenges, strengths, and innovation capacities. A key goal is to establish food innovation platforms, collaborative hubs for researchers, businesses, policymakers, and citizens. Based on co-creation, open science and RRI principles, the project produces acceleration agendas, builds networks for knowledge sharing and aims to create a guidebook for sustainable food systems across Europe.”

FEASTS is a collaborative research EU Horizon Europe with the goal to deliver a comprehensive, unbiased knowledge base about cultured meat and seafood (CM/CSF), and their place in the food system. FEAST attended the General Assembly of FEASTS in 2025 in Amsterdam, joined the sessions, and created synergies between different work packages to support scientific knowledge exchange.

Sister projects **PLAN'EAT** and **SWITCH**

In addition to the above projects, FEAST explored opportunities for collaboration with the two sister projects *PLAN'EAT* and *SWITCH* which are funded under the same Horizon Europe Farm2Fork call as FEAST.

All three projects are complementary and supplementary in using similar approaches and methods (e.g. use of living labs and policy labs/dialogues), which are presenting important opportunities for synergy and collaboration.

Furthermore, FEAST is collaborating with WHO Europe³ (engagement has already begun), the Good Food Finance Network⁴ (engagement has already begun), and the Regional Office for Europe of the World Health Organization.

The FEAST hackathons had multiple collaborations with external organizations and projects like the *King's Health Partners*, *HIN - Health Innovation Network South London*, and *NHS South East London Integrated Care System*, co-organized the second FEAST hackathon in London to support people in Southeast London to live healthier lifestyles and adopt healthier diets.

³ <https://www.who.int/europe/about-us/about-who-europe> (accessed on 15.11.2022)

⁴ <https://goodfood.finance/> (accessed on 15.11.2022)

In Kaunas FEAST partnered with *Kaunas University of Technology*, VIVITA Lithuania, *the Lithuanian University of Health Sciences*, and *Design Friends* to help children and their families/caregivers lead a better lifestyle and eat healthier.

The Berlin hackathon was initiated and successfully conducted in collaboration with the Berlin *Community Garden Programme* of the Berlin Department for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action, and the Environment.

Further collaboration partners for the hackathon's final event in Copenhagen included the *BEACON project* and the *Copenhagen Business School*.

Projects completed in 2023.

- **FOODSHIFT2030** (H2020 - Susmetro, Commune d'Avignon, INRAE): In partnership with engaged citizens, NGOs, SMEs, researchers, local administration, and policy makers, FOODSHIFT2030 has established nine living labs across Europe to incubate local food system innovations.

FEAST's contribution: FoodSHIFT 2030 Policy Conference. Keynote and panel debate with input on FEAST.

- **Join Action Best-ReMaP** (EuroHealthNet): a Europe-wide Joint Action (2020-2023) that seeks to contribute to an improved quality of food supplied to citizens of Europe by facilitating the exchange and testing of good practices concerning: i) the monitoring and analysis of how the food that people consume changes at the European and national level; ii) the regulations on the marketing of food and beverages to children and; iii) the procurement of food by public bodies for educational institutions, social care facilities, etc..

FEAST's contribution: FEAST's DEC team is working BestReMap on a strategy to promote the results from the BestReMap project.

- **COACH** (H2020 – ICLEI): This project facilitates collaboration between farmers, consumers, local governments and other actors to scale up short agri-food chains.

6 Obligations and requirements for communication actions

6.1 Information on EU funding

As FEAST receives funding from the EU, Innovate UK and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) we use the logo Co-funded by the European Union in our DEC activities as described in article 17 of the GA.

Figure 24 Logos used in FEAST for information on EU funding

6.2 Disclaimer excluding agency and commission responsibility

FEAST disclaimer statements include:

“FEAST is co-funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101060536. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK participant in FEAST (Good Food Oxfordshire) is supported by Innovate UK grant number 10041509 and the Swiss participant in FEAST (FiBL) is supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 22.00156.”

In addition to this, FEAST-specific disclaimers are also included:

- Project No 101060536.
- This work was supported by Innovate UK [grant number 10041509] and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 22.00156.
- Start Date 01/07/2022, End Date 30/06/2027

7 Reflections on lessons learned

Effective communication ideally promotes the activities and results of a project, attracts experts, increases collaboration and engagement with end users, makes citizens aware of how public money is spent, and creates visibility. Dissemination activities support sharing research results with the scientific community, commercial players, civil society, and policymakers. During the first reporting period, FEAST carried out more than 80 individual communication and over 20 dissemination activities, not including individual social media posts by FEAST and FEAST partners.

As described in Section 2, FEAST's methodology for DEC activities involves five steps (identify target audience and messages, select tools, plan and implement activities) in a continuous loop.

The following reflections on lessons learned can be drawn after 17 months of the project:

- Digital platforms are essential for good internal communication within the team and with the communication teams of the partners.
- The use of templates for presentations and reports facilitates a common visual language.
- The production of materials in local languages enables access to local stakeholders. See for example, the [YouTube videos on the Living Labs](#)
- Social media allows FEAST to reach a wide, targeted audience, maximizing FEAST’s impact and successfully exploiting our project results. Social media is being used for both our communication and dissemination. Before launching our project on a specific social media platform, the pros and cons of each specific platform need to be evaluated. As social media platforms evolve over time, projects like FEAST are always in the situation to evaluate their strategies. Questions like:
 - Does the platform share the values of the project?
 - Is the audience we want to reach changing?
 - Is the business model of the platform changing, and might this impact the project?
 - Are we also reaching our collaborators via the platform, i.e. other projects?

- Cross-platform linking (LinkedIn, partner websites, FEAST's website, newsletter, etc.) enables easier access to our materials.
- Some audiences are known at the start of the project, and others are not. The communication material should, therefore, be created in such a way that communication can adapt accordingly to changing needs.
- Regular analysis of the activities enables readjustment and continuous improvement.

8 Showcasing Best Practices

In the second DEC update, we introduce a new section about best practices to showcase the learnings, findings, and challenges we faced in producing communication materials, disseminating, and exploiting project results. These examples could be relevant for other projects, communities engaging with local stakeholders, and organizations that want to gain visibility.

We aim to provide best practices for most of the DEC activities by the end of the FEAST project in order to show how the project worked on achieving it's main objectives:

- To create and **communicate** content to boost the visibility and support engagement of food and health system stakeholders (including media and public) with FEAST objectives and activities, through both traditional media (brochures, booklets, etc.) and digital media (i.e., website, electronic newsletters, podcasts).
- To **disseminate** project results to internal and external target audiences through scientific and other channels (i.e., community talks, workshops) at European and local levels.
- To utilise project results and improve the transfer of technical and scientific knowledge outside the core consortium to facilitate the **exploitation** of results.

The FEAST DEC best practices are established as internal workflows to achieve the project goals. Regarding content creation and increasing visibility, we focused on building the relevant channels and establishing them as a valuable resource for our stakeholders.

The following three examples highlight the practices undertaken in FEAST that have proven effective. These practices include: activities in living labs (Figure 25), online webinars (Figure 26), and sharing information on trusted platforms (Figure 27).

8.1 Best Practice for Living Lab activities

To support the local activities of our Living Labs, we have established a mechanism to create content for local channels (i.e. in local languages) as well as international European stakeholders. Together with the Living Lab coordinator, we decided on the best time to produce communication materials. Depending on their activities, os4os visits the Living Lab with production equipment (e.g. video and audio recording tools) and engages with a local expert who knows FEAST and the local partners' objectives best. In consultation with the local expert, we create an outline of the key themes, stakeholders and content types to be created. The choice of who we invite to do an interview is mainly strategic, keeping in mind who is relevant for the local Living Lab to get support from.

As an example, in LL Guldborgsbund in Denmark (<https://www.guldborgsbund.dk/om-kommunen/internationalt-samarbejde/oversigt-over-igangvaerende-internationale-projekter/feast>), we have visited the cooking school and Carina Woollhead (Local Living Lab Lead)

interviewed the local mayor of Nykobingen. He played a leading role in showing the municipality's support for healthy food for school children and was visible to decision-makers in other municipalities in Denmark, too. The local media were also invited to the event, which ended in a local news report about the activity.

As a production outcome of the visit to Guldborgsbund Municipality, we have published an eight minute video with the mayor and video impressions of the cooking school with kids, all in Danish. The English subtitles added to the video increase the international reach.

This was uploaded to our [FEAST YouTube channel](#) – and with a LinkedIn post, we promoted the activity as well as the video.

Dedicated Living Lab videos are always produced in the local language and English subtitles are added afterwards. For the Best Practice video, we decided to have one “general” language, English, and add subtitles in all the other languages where the speaker came from. This supports the Living Labs by giving them the opportunity to increase their local visibility and gain more stakeholder support. The videos can be more easily embedded on their websites, and speakers usually feel more comfortable speaking in their native language.

Figure 25 Best practice Living Lab activities communication – DEC outcomes to boost visibility

What we did:

Producing communication material for FEAST channels and municipality channels. Interview and photos of a cooking session and the mayor of the municipality of Guldborgsund.

Recording two short podcast episodes with the Guldborgsund Living Lab coordinator and an external partner from a local industrial kitchen, which could potentially support the Living Lab’s activities. A third episode connecting the two recorded ones has been produced after this visit with policy experts from another FEAST partner in Denmark.

How we did it:

Video recording, photo series, podcast recording, social media communication

Return rate:

The FEAST LL coordinator in Guldborgsund gained national recognition and is seen as an expert in Denmark on the importance of children’s nutrition and education in schools. With the work done in FEAST, the municipality set the base to apply for national funding to become a pilot of the Danish School Food Project.

8.2 Best practice online webinars

EuroHealthNet in collaboration with os4os hosted public Policy Chats Webinars. The aim was to have policy dialogues on specific topics. For each webinar, the EuroHealthNet team invited three speakers who had 30 minutes to present on a relevant topic.

Since the start of the pandemic, many events have moved online. But this has also made people feel tired of online events. In order to recruit participants for the webinars, it became apparent that sufficient time needed to be allocated for the promotion of the sessions and their distribution across a range of networks and channels.

Figure 26 Best practice online webinars – DEC outcomes to boost visibility and disseminate outcomes

What we did:

Hosting an open webinar with registered participants and sharing the presentations after the session, they were made available for download in our Resource section on the website. The webinar recordings have been edited and uploaded to our YouTube channel. For the second Policy Chat in January 2025, each speaker's session was transformed into a blog post as well.

How we did it:

Set up an event landing page on the FEAST website with details about the speaker sessions and created an Eventbrite event on the platform (<https://www.eventbrite.com/>) to organize the registrations and run marketing campaigns.

For marketing and recruiting participants, we made LinkedIn campaigns where we presented the webinar in general and each speaker's session, highlighting their topics and background.

Speaker onboarding and equipment test beforehand to ensure proper set up. This was done with Microsoft Teams Professional, where the presentations are uploaded beforehand, and the organizer can manage who is visible on the screen, who can access the slides, what regular webinar visitors see and how they can contribute to discussions.

After the webinar in the post-production, the recordings were edited and divided into three parts for each speaker. This gave us the possibility to upload three videos instead of one very long video on YouTube and have each session title as a headline on the video platform, which is relevant to search engines. The connection to our website and YouTube is closing the loop and increases the project's visibility.

Return rate:

The first Policy Chat webinar on March 4th, 2024 had 226 registrations. The second Policy Chat webinar on January 25th had 184 registrations.

8.3 Best practice visibility on Trusted Platforms

Zenodo is an open research repository to share and preserve all forms of research outputs, including data, software, publications, and other digital artefacts. It assigns Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to submissions, making research outputs citable. Zenodo is hosted by CERN and funded by the European Commission through the OpenAIRE project.

FEAST deliverables and reports have been made publicly available on the FEAST website and Zenodo since the start of the project. A FEAST project “Zenodo Community” was created to host all project-specific outputs. There are currently (15.06.2025) 15 Records that can be downloaded through the FEAST Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/feast/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>). The use of Zenodo supports FEAST's strong commitment to open science.

Figure 27 Best practice Trusted Platforms – DEC disseminating outcomes

What we did:

Create a community on Zenodo to manage all uploads and have them displayed in an overview. By the end of the project, the FEAST Community will have a rich library of documents, datasets, tools, and materials to be used, all of which will be aligned with the FAIR principles.

How we did it:

Set up a workflow for the consortium where the roles are defined, e.g., who is uploading on Zenodo, when we upload, and what consequences a DOI has on the changes we make after the submission.

Cleaning and double-checking files and datasets before upload, if they are machine-readable and cleaned.

Return rate:

In June 2025, there were a total of 1668 downloads across the 15 available records on Zenodo.

9 Conclusion

FEAST's DEC approach aims to incorporate evidence-based and state of the art practices to support the efficient and effective utilisation of FEAST's results to build capacity at the micro, meso and macro level of Europe's food systems to empower and enable stakeholders to transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour and ensure that these changes 'stick'. Table 26 summarises the target audiences, their needs, FEAST's expected results related to these target audiences as well as the DEC approaches that will be used to achieve these results.

Table 26 Summary and mapping of specific needs identified, expected results and DEC measures

Specific Needs	Expected Results	D & E & C Approaches
<p>We currently have 'Lose-Lose-Lose-Win' food systems in Europe where only large businesses 'Win' at the expense of people, planet, public sector and small enterprises.</p> <p>People</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NCD-linked morbidity and mortality linked to poor quality diets (75% of all diseases and 85% of all deaths in Europe can be attributed to NCDs). - Increased health inequalities and food insecurity. <p>Planet</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Huge GHG and environmental burden stemming from dietary choices (26% of GHG emissions, 50% of global habitable land use, 70% of freshwater use, 78% of eutrophication and 60% of biodiversity loss). <p>Public Sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7-10% of GDP, 70% of healthcare budgets (~€700 billion) spent on NCDs. <p>Private Sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Struggling primary producers (average EU 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Established baselines and sampling tools for ongoing monitoring, that can be used in the short-, medium- and long-term to understand the health and sustainability metrics of the food system at all levels (micro, meso, macro). 2. An integrated health and sustainability impact assessment approach, including scenario modelling, for solutions on organizational, municipal, national and EU levels that can be used to understand costs and benefits of different food system solutions in the medium-long term. 3. Tools, policies and programmes that can empower European food systems actors (micro, meso, macro levels) to support just transitions to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour. 4. A toolbox of effective co-created solutions (community, technology) that can be leveraged by food system actors, including policymakers, to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable diets. 5. A co-designed set of communication strategies and tactics that can be used by EU policymakers at all levels of government as well as interest groups, retailers, education systems and the media to facilitate dissemination and monitoring of effective solutions to facilitate the transition to healthier and more sustainable diets. 	<p>Dissemination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FEAST Community of Practice (leveraging 1800 fab labs, 1750 city network; 57 public health bodies). - At least 10 FEAST open access scientific publications; development of evidence-based policy recommendations; participation in (after year 2) at least: 3 conferences/year; 2 local community-based talks/year through our NGO and public sector partners; one hands-on workshop/year. - Open Science datasets and scientific publications (14 research partners, OS infrastructure, 3 Lancet Commissions including EAT Lancet 2.0). <p>Exploitation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8-12 replicator cities (outside of FEAST consortium) take up FEAST solutions. - Uptake, scaling and development of the Open Source Educational Kit (for children, teachers, parents) via 3,000 schools involved in SchoolFood4Change. - Use of FEAST open datasets and models. - Build/expand CAxP & EFMs (current reach of 1.5 million citizens). - Empower 10,000s of consumers across Europe via <i>myLabel</i> app. <p>Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regularly updated FEAST website. - Traditional media campaigns.

<p>farmer earns ~50% of the average EU worker) and SMEs.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Social media campaigns & online events.- Science cafes.
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Annex

Annex 1 – Partner websites, social media channels and specific sites and channels

Table A1 1 FEAST organisation websites and links to FEAST on the partners websites

Partner	Hyperlink
University of Heidelberg	https://www.uni-heidelberg.de/en <i>FEAST on the HIGH website</i>
Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alto Minho	http://www.cim-altominho.pt
NCSR “Demokritos”	https://www.demokritos.gr
EuroHealthNet	https://eurohealthnet.eu <i>FEAST on the EuroHealthNet website</i>
Roskilde University	https://ruc.dk
EAT Foundation	https://eatforum.org <i>FEAST on the EAT website</i>
Sciensano	https://www.sciensano.be/en <i>FEAST on the Sciensano website</i>
Arete	https://aretenet.org
University College Cork	https://www.ucc.ie/en
Ökosoziales Forum Österreich & Europa	https://oekosozial.at
ICLEI Europe	https://iclei-europe.org
Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture	https://www.inrae.fr <i>FEAST on the INRAE website</i>
Institut de Recherche Pour Le Development	https://www.ird.fr
Louis Bolk Institute	https://louisbolk.nl/en
myLabel	https://mylabel.io
open science for open societies	https://os4os.org/en <i>FEAST on the os4os website</i>
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	https://www.santannapisa.it/en

Susmetro	https://www.susmetro.eu <i>FEAST on the Susmetro website</i>
Università degli Studi di Scienze Gastronomiche	https://www.unisg.it/en
Commune d'Avignon	http://www.avignon.fr
University of Graz	https://www.uni-graz.at/en
Instituto Politecnico de Viana de Castelo	https://www.ipvc.pt/en
OpenDot	http://www.opendotlab.it <i>FEAST on the OpenDot website</i>
Opshtina Prilep	https://www.prilep.gov.mk
University of Lodz	https://www.uni.lodz.pl/en
Municipality of Sitia	https://www.sitia.gr
LEADER-Region Weinviertel Donauraum	http://www.leaderwd.at
Katholieke University of Leuven	https://www.kuleuven.be/english
Leuven2030	https://www.leuven2030.be <i>FEAST on the Leuven 2030 website</i>
City of Gent	https://stad.gent
Azienda USL Toscana	http://www.uslnordovest.toscana.it
City of Rotterdam	https://www.rotterdam.nl
Guldborg Municipality	https://www.guldborgsund.dk <i>FEAST on the Guldborg Municipality website</i>
Good Food Oxfordshire	https://goodfoodoxford.org
Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau	https://www.fibl.org <i>FEAST on the FIBL website</i>

Annex 2 – Brief Work Package Description

WP 1 & 9 - Project Management & Ethics requirements

The overall purpose of the activity is to provide project management and coordination for the FEAST project across all other activities. All partners will contribute to effective management through a contract and delivery of technical and financial reports.

WP2 - Mapping & monitoring dietary patterns

Current research on mapping and monitoring dietary behaviours is limited to a few EU countries using different survey focuses, methods, and tools. The most popular 'food frequency questionnaire', for example, can measure adherence to healthy diets and in few cases minimally or partially capture the behavioural and communication aspect of food that leads to improved healthy diets. Our approach will advance the state of the art by first reviewing current literature and subsequently improving and integrating tools while applying robust methods including cross-sectional surveys, experiments and the collection of primary data through citizen science initiatives to triangulate our data and overcome these limitations. Our aim will be to fully capture which foods are over- and under-consumed by vulnerable societal groups and the factors influencing their behaviours. These insights will support the development of targeted strategies for specific population segments to enable the transition to healthier and more sustainable diets.

WP3 - Mapping and Monitoring factors that shape food environments

Food environments (consisting of public and private sectors as well as communities) have an important role in determining the types of food citizens have access to. The individual and collective actions of these sectors will, to a large extent, determine the opportunities that citizens have to eat healthy and sustainable diets. We will apply rigorous methods to gain insight into the roles of business, governments and communities in influencing the transition to healthier and more sustainable food environments in line with Farm2Fork aims. The overarching objective here is to improve our understanding of the barriers and enabling factors affecting food system actors' efforts to improve food environments and to produce, process, promote and provide affordable, sufficient, healthy and environmentally, socially and economically sustainable food products, processes and services to respond to citizens' needs, requirements and preferences.

WP4 - Co-developed community-based solutions

Food systems across Europe are very heterogeneous. Despite the fact that different areas will face similar problems (such as high consumption of unhealthy/unsustainable diets, especially among vulnerable groups), the root causes that lead to and perpetuate these problems will be different across different contexts. This means that it will not be possible to create one-size-fits all solutions for these problems and it means that co-created solutions that account for local contextual factors will be essential to effectively tackle these problems. The overarching objective of WP4 is to co-develop community-based solutions to support the just transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour.

WP5 - Co-developed tech-based solutions

Technology-based solutions can play a very important role in supporting the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours at the micro and meso-levels of food systems. The goal of WP5 is to design novel technology-based solutions, scale solutions and evaluate the causal impact of existing technologies for promoting the transitions to healthier and more sustainable diets, particularly in vulnerable groups. These solutions will be tested for both individuals and communities.

WP6 - Understanding and measuring the impacts

Our goal with this WP is to work on a common modelling framework that can be used across regions (both cities and rural areas) with a vision of weaving outcomes together for regional and global comparative analyses. Simulation models that are able to more clearly articulate how actions on a micro level are going to have an impact on a macro level can be used to design solutions at a macro level and vice versa. The applicability for policy makers will be key and the produced model will be as easy to handle as possible. Formally, the model will make it possible to i) characterise and prioritise the determinants of food system evolution and ii) assess the impacts of public actions or changes in behaviours. Our approach will directly address the challenge of building an architecture that takes into account the heterogeneity of the nature of the information and the scales of relations.

WP7 - Policy dialogues to inform food system governance

The primary objective of WP7 is to co-design policy and recommendations for policymakers using a policy dialogue methodology underpinned by scientific evidence and stakeholder engagement to facilitate the transition towards healthy and sustainable diets. The key output will be a road-map and set of policy briefs identifying opportunities across different policy levels, involving different food system actors, to achieve a fairer/more equal transition to healthy and sustainable dietary behaviours.

WP8 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

FEAST is designed to create a paradigm shift for food systems to ones that are fairer, healthier and more environmentally friendly for all actors (primary production to consumption), particularly vulnerable populations. Our pathway to impact will begin by working through our Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) to leverage the results and outputs from FEAST to ensure broad-scale strategic dissemination of the project's findings and key messages, enabling their uptake and integration in future strategies and practices developed by local, regional and national governments, and simultaneously engaging the general public (consumers, citizens), production/supply side actors and young professionals in the implementation of such strategies - thus inspiring each target group to move upwards in the engagement pyramid, and further exploiting FEAST's potential to build capacity. The dissemination and exploitation planning will ensure the generated results achieve FEAST's intended outcomes and maximises the overall impacts of the project by efficiently reaching clearly defined stakeholders through wide-reaching communication activities, efficient dissemination and impactful capacity building. The overarching objective of WP8 is to raise levels of awareness of food systems actors, including citizens, about transition towards healthy and sustainable food behaviours.

Annex 3 – Links and statistics related FEAST's website and social media use and activities

Table A3 1 Full list of FEAST YouTube videos, ranked by views

Title	Video publish time	Views
FEAST Trailer	12.07.2023	553
Hackathon Milan 2023 Trailer	06.06.2023	237
Happy FEAST-O-Ween 2022	28.10.2022	219
Good Food Oxfordshire a FEAST Living Lab	23.01.2023	193
FEAST Kick Off Impressions	13.10.2022	188
Hack for Food, Hack for Good, FEAST Hackathon Milan 2023, Dr. Anant Jani	26.06.2023	170
FEAST Policy Chat 01 - Does manipulation of food culture impact food system policy (Part 01)	16.04.2024	165
FEAST Living Labs: Best Practices	10.03.2025	163
Leuven 2030 a FEAST Living Lab	07.02.2023	159
CIM Alto Minho a FEAST Living Lab	06.04.2023	149
Ghent a FEAST Living Lab	14.03.2023	143
Tuscany a FEAST Living Lab	10.07.2023	142
Rotterdam – Beijerlandsewaan / Groene Hilledijk a FEAST Living Lab	06.02.2023	133
Prilep a FEAST Living Lab	23.03.2023	130
Guldborgsund Municipality a FEAST Living Lab	07.03.2023	127
Food School Sakskøbing - Teaching kids how to cook	28.02.2024	124
FEAST Policy Chat 02 - Food systems in times of shock (Part01)	31.01.2025	115
Hack for Good Hack for Food - London 2024 - Impressions	01.03.2024	107
Avignon a FEAST Living Lab	21.02.2023	100
FEAST General Assembly Impressions	17.12.2024	95
Sitia Municipality a FEAST Living Lab	10.03.2023	90
Granola - Breakfast in a bowl	15.10.2024	89
Hack for Food, Hack for Good, FEAST Hackathon Milan 2023, Nicolas	27.06.2023	86

HubCity Milan – as outcome of the FEAST hackathon	04.06.2024	75
FEAST Policy Chat 02 - Outcomes and Externalities of a Competitive Food System (Part 02)	31.01.2025	73
Lodz a FEAST Living Lab	19.03.2023	72
Side dish - Simple, fresh, and full of flavor!	18.10.2024	71
CFPC EUPHA2023 Presentation Workshop	17.11.2023	70
One plate, endless nourishment!	18.10.2024	69
LEADER Weinviertel Donauraum	18.08.2023	67
FEAST Policy Chat 02 - What are the alternative food systems that are before us?	31.01.2025	63
Hackathon London – Specialist weight management – Part 3	06.06.2024	60
Mapping & Monitoring Factors that Shape Food Environment - BIA outcome	09.12.2024	55
Hackathon London – King's Health Partners – Part 2	06.06.2024	53
FEAST x LIMA VISIT	20.12.2024	52
FEAST Policy Chat 01 - Does manipulation of food culture impact food system policy (Part 03)	16.04.2024	52
Hackathon Milan 2023 Interview Elisa	26.06.2023	51
FEAST x MINHO VISIT	20.12.2024	49
The KeizGarden Wheel: Behind the Scenes	24.03.2025	46
Hack for Food, Hack for Good, FEAST Hackathon Milan 2023, Francesca	27.06.2023	45
Hackathon London –Participant from Good Food Oxfordshire – Part 4	06.06.2024	45
FEAST holidays 2022	19.12.2022	43
FEAST Policy Chat 01- Does manipulation of food culture impact food system policy (Part 02)	16.04.2024	42
A healthy meal to go!	18.10.2024	41
Hackathon London Prototypes - Dissemination Webinar	17.12.2024	41
Hackathon London – Introduction – Part 1	06.06.2024	35
Hackathon London - Collaboration & Co-creation - Part 7	02.07.2024	33
Carrot cake - Where health meets delicious!	18.10.2024	32

Hackathon London - Challenges - Part 5	12.06.2024	31
Meet Katharina: Participant from Berlin Hackathon	28.04.2025	28
Meet Toni: Participant from our Berlin Hackathon	29.04.2025	28
Community Gardens & Innovation: Behind-the-scenes Talk!	08.04.2025	27
Hackathon London - Methodology - Part 6	02.07.2024	23
Sneak-Peek of our LEADER Weinviertel-Donauraum Living Lab	25.03.2025	23
Hack for Good Hack for Food - Berlin 2024 – Impressions	14.04.2025	21
Hack for Good Hack for Food - Kaunas 2024 – Impressions	17.12.2024	21
Happy FEASTgiving!	27.11.2024	18
Merry X-Mas	24.12.2024	8

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